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SIEBERT, L.

Energy Crops and Erosion Control in Germany in the Context of the Bioeconomy Strategy

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Department of Soil System Science
Theodor-Lieser-Str. 4 | 06120 Halle (Saale), Germany
Phone: (+49) 345 558 5226 | E-Mail: info@bonares.de
www.bonares.de

Title Energy Crops and Erosion Control in Germany in the Context of the Bioeconomy Strategy

Authors Siebert, Lea – Technical University Berlin (TU), Berlin

Correspondence lea.siebert@posteo.de

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Abstract In the context of climate change and a steadily rising demand for energy, the concept of a bioeconomy stands for a shift from fossil fuels to bio-based energy sources. In Germany the National Strategy on Bioeconomy promotes biomass as an energy carrier to meet the federal government's ambitious targets for bioenergy generation. Inevitably, this requires an expansion of energy crop cultivation, which increases pressures on soil resources by reducing soil resistance to erosive forces. Policies need to ensure that an intensification of energy crop cultivation is not increasing soil degradation, as soil is not only crucial for the bioeconomy, but also contributes to the provision of several ecosystem services. As soil erosion by water is the most severe threat to European soil, the focus was on regulations for erosion control. The policy analysis of relevant legislation at EU, national and regional level and the GIS-analysis of regional implementation practices revealed several shortcomings: Only few policy instruments set binding standards for erosion control. Furthermore, local authorities can undermine the risk assessment process and the resulting soil management restrictions. The GIS-analysis revealed an underestimation of erosion risk of approx. 24 %, regarding the total area of Saxony, which was chosen as an example. This could be linked to a low quality of data within the assessment process. Local authorities balancing farmer's interests and soil conservation were identified as another risk, which has the potential to significantly decrease the effectiveness of the current legislation. In cases of noncompliance with compulsory requirements subsidies can be reduced. However, due to limited resources, on-the-spot-checks are rare and penalties not necessarily transparent.

Keywords BonaRes, soil research, bioeconomy, energy crops, erosion control

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Abstract

In the context of climate change and a steadily rising demand for energy, the concept of a bioeconomy stands for a shift from fossil fuels to bio-based energy sources. In Germany the *National Strategy on Bioeconomy* promotes biomass as an energy carrier to meet the federal government's ambitious targets for bioenergy generation. Inevitably, this requires an expansion of energy crop cultivation, which increases pressures on soil resources by reducing soil resistance to erosive forces. Policies need to ensure that an intensification of energy crop cultivation is not increasing soil degradation, as soil is not only crucial for the bioeconomy, but also contributes to the provision of several ecosystem services. Within this master's thesis the suitability of existing legislation to ensure sustainable energy crop production was evaluated and recommendations were given for an adjustment of policy instruments. As soil erosion by water is the most severe threat to European soil, the focus was on regulations for erosion control. This work was done within the scope of the BonaRes (*soil as a sustainable resource for bioeconomy*) programme. The policy analysis of relevant legislation at EU, national and regional level and the GIS-analysis of regional implementation practices revealed several shortcomings: Only few policy instruments set binding standards for erosion control. Furthermore, local authorities can undermine the risk assessment process and the resulting soil management restrictions. The GIS-analysis revealed an underestimation of erosion risk of approx. 24 %, regarding the total area of Saxony, which was chosen as an example. This could be linked to a low quality of data within the assessment process. Local authorities balancing farmer's interests and soil conservation were identified as another risk, which has the potential to significantly decrease the effectiveness of the current legislation. In cases of non-compliance with compulsory requirements subsidies can be reduced. However, due to limited resources, on-the-spot-checks are rare and penalties not necessarily transparent. Recommendations given as a result of this thesis comprise increasing the binding force of erosion control regulations, considering regional rainfall erosivity as a compulsory factor in erosion risk assessment, and making the use of most recent data mandatory. Furthermore, an Ecological Risk Assessment Framework was proposed for the consideration of both, local environmental and crop-specific factors. According to the resulting risk matrix it is recommended to ban cultivation of energy crops with highest impact intensity from fields with a very high susceptibility to soil erosion by water. The approach developed for the proposed framework can also be used to underpin future funding schemes for sustainable biomass-to-energy production. However, a comprehensive assessment of environmental risks requires additional data from field trials as well as the consideration of further environmental impacts.

Zusammenfassung

Im Kontext von Klimawandel und eines stetig steigenden Energiebedarfs steht das Konzept der Bioökonomie für einen Umstieg von fossilen Brennstoffen auf biobasierte Energieträger. In Deutschland bewirbt die *Nationale Politikstrategie Bioökonomie* die Nutzung von Biomasse als Energiequelle, um die ehrgeizigen Bioenergieziele der Bundesregierung zu erreichen. Hierfür ist die Ausweitung des Anbaus von Energiepflanzen unabdingbar, was den Druck auf die Ressource Boden erhöht und ihn gegenüber erosiven Kräften schwächt. Da Böden nicht nur für die Bioökonomie von Bedeutung sind, sondern auch darüber hinaus zur Bereitstellung verschiedener Ökosystemdienstleistungen beitragen, muss die Politik dafür sorgen, dass eine Intensivierung des Energiepflanzenanbaus nicht zu einem Anstieg der Bodendegradation führt. Im Rahmen dieser Masterarbeit wurde untersucht, ob die existierende Gesetzgebung geeignet ist, eine nachhaltige Energiepflanzenproduktion sicherzustellen. Darüber hinaus wurden Empfehlungen formuliert, um Politikinstrumente entsprechend anzupassen. Da Bodenerosion durch Wasser für Böden in Europa die größte Gefahr darstellt, lag der Fokus auf Regelungen zum Erosionsschutz. Diese Arbeit wurde im Rahmen des BonaRes (*Boden als nachhaltige Ressource für die Bioökonomie*) Programms verfasst. Die Auswertung der relevanten gesetzlichen Regelungen auf EU-, nationaler und regionaler Ebene sowie die GIS-Analyse der praktischen Umsetzung auf regionaler Ebene legte einige Defizite offen: Nur wenige Politikinstrumente legen verbindliche Standards zum Erosionsschutz fest, während örtliche Behörden den Prozess der Risikoeinschätzung sowie die daraus folgenden Auflagen zur Bodenbewirtschaftung unterlaufen können. Die GIS-Auswertung offenbarte eine auf schlechte Datengrundlage zurückgehende Unterbewertung des Erosionsrisikos auf ca. 24 % der Fläche des Beispielbundeslandes Sachsen. Ein weiteres Risiko für die Effektivität der aktuellen Gesetzgebung stellt die Abwägung zwischen den Interessen der LandwirtInnen und des Bodenschutzes durch die örtlichen Behörden dar. Auch wenn Verstöße gegen verbindliche Vorgaben zu einer Kürzung von Subventionen führen können, so sind die Mittel für Kontrollen vor Ort begrenzt und auferlegte Sanktionen nicht unbedingt nachvollziehbar. Als Ergebnis dieser Arbeit wird empfohlen, die Verbindlichkeit der Vorgaben zum Erosionsschutz zu erhöhen, die Niederschlagserosivität als obligatorischen Faktor in die Risikobewertung mit einzubeziehen und die Verwendung aktuellster Daten verpflichtend zu machen. Außerdem wurde eine Ökologische Risikoeinschätzung für die Berücksichtigung sowohl ortsbezogener als auch pflanzenbezogener Faktoren vorgestellt. Die daraus resultierende Risikomatrix sieht ein Verbot von Energiepflanzen mit hoher Wirkungsintensität auf Feldern mit hoher Empfindlichkeit gegenüber Wassererosion vor. Der hier entwickelte Ansatz kann auch für die Förderung von nachhaltigem Biomasseanbau zur Energieproduktion dienen. Allerdings sind für eine umfassende Bewertung der Umweltrisiken sowohl zusätzliche Felddaten als auch die Berücksichtigung weiterer Umweltauswirkungen nötig.

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List of Abbreviations

ABAG	Universal Soil Loss Equation in Germany (Allgemeine Bodenabtragungsgleichung)
AECM	Agri-Environment Climate Measures
AEE	Renewable Energies Agency (Agentur für Erneuerbare Energien)
AgrarZahlVerpflG	Agricultural Payments Act (Agrarzahlungen-Verpflichtungengesetz)
AgrarZahlVerpflV	Agricultural Payments Act (Agrarzahlungen-Verpflichtungsverordnungen)
AUK	Agri-Environment-Climate Measures in Saxony (Agrarumwelt- und Klimamaßnahmen)
BBodSchG	Soil Protection Act (Bundes-Bodenschutzgesetz)
BBodSchV	Federal Soil Protection and Contaminated Sites Ordinance (Bundes-Bodenschutzverordnung)
BGR	Institute for Geosciences and Natural Resources (Bundesanstalt für Geowissenschaften und Rohstoffe)
BImSchG	Federal Immission Control Act (Bundes-Immissionsschutzgesetz)
Biokraft-NachV	Biofuel Sustainability Ordinance (Biokraftstoff-Nachhaltigkeitsverordnung)
BiomasseV	Biomass Ordinance (Biomasseverordnung)
BioSt-NachV	Biomass Electricity Sustainability Ordinance (Biomassestrom-Nachhaltigkeitsverordnung)
BLE	Federal Office for Agriculture and Food (Bundesministerium für Landwirtschaft und Ernährung)
BMBF	Federal Ministry of Education and Research (Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung)
BonaRes	Soil as a sustainable resource for the bioeconomy (Boden als nachhaltige Ressource für die Bioökonomie)
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CICES	Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services
CO_{2eq}	carbon dioxide equivalent
DirektzahlDurchfG	Direct Payments Act (Direktzahlungen-Durchführungsgesetz)
DirektzahlDurchfV	Direct Payments Ordinance (Direktzahlungen-Durchführungsverordnung)
DM	dry matter content
DPSIR	Driver-Pressure-State-Impact-Response

DWD	German Meteorological Service (Deutscher Wetterdienst)
EEG	Renewable Energy Sources Act (Erneuerbare-Energien-Gesetz)
EEWärmeG	Renewable Energy Heat Act (Erneuerbare-Energien-Wärmegesetz)
E_{nat}	natural erosion risk
EAFRD	European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development
EAGF	European Agricultural Guarantee Fund
ErosionsSchV	Regulation on erosion control in Baden-Wuerttemberg (Erosionsschutzverordnung)
EschV	Regulation on erosion control in Bavaria (Erosionsschutzverordnung)
FNR	Agency for Renewable Resources (Fachagentur Nachwachsende Rohstoffe e.V.)
GAK	Joint Task for the Improvement of Agricultural Structures and Coastal Protection (Gemeinschaftsaufgabe "Verbesserung der Agrarstruktur und des Küstenschutzes")
GAKG	Joint Task for the Improvement of Agricultural Structures and Coastal Protection Act (Gesetz über die Gemeinschaftsaufgabe "Verbesserung der Agrarstruktur und des Küstenschutzes")
GAEC	Good Agricultural and Environmental Condition
GeoSN	Geoinformation and Land Survey Saxony (Geobasisinformation und Vermessung Sachsen)
GHG	greenhouse gas
GIS	geographical information system
iLUC	indirect land-use change
JRC	Joint Research Centre
KULAP	Cultural Landscape Programme in Bavaria (Kulturlandschaftsprogramm)
LABO	Federal State Soil Protection Working Group (Bund/Länder-Arbeitsgemeinschaft Bodenschutz)
LfL	Bavarian State Research Centre for Agriculture (Bayerische Landesanstalt für Landwirtschaft)
LfULG	Saxon State Office for the Environment, Agriculture and Geology (Sächsisches Landesamt für Umwelt, Landwirtschaft und Geologie)
MJ	megajoule
NRR	National Framework for Rural Development (Nationale Rahmenregelung der Bundesrepublik Deutschland)

OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PJ	petajoule
RDP	Rural Development Programme
RUSLE	Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation
SächsGapAnfVO	Regulation on erosion control in Saxony (Sächsische GAP-Anforderungenverordnung)
SMUL	Saxon State Ministry for the Environment and Agriculture (Sächsisches Staatsministerium für Umwelt und Landwirtschaft)
SMR	Statutory Management Requirements
SOC	soil organic content
SOM	soil organic matter
SRF	short-rotation forestry
SRU	German Advisory Council on the Environment (Sachverständigenrat für Umweltfragen)
TEEB	The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity
UBA	German Environment Agency (Umweltbundesamt)
USLE	Universal Soil Loss Equation
VwV FAKT	Administrative Regulation on the Support Programme for Agri-Environment, Climate Protection and Animal Welfare (Verwaltungsvorschrift des Ministeriums für Ländlichen Raum und Verbraucherschutz zum Förderprogramm für Agrarumwelt, Klimaschutz und Tierwohl)

1 Introduction

In response to global challenges such as a growing world population, climate change and a limited and constantly degrading natural capital, the German *National Strategy on Bioeconomy* calls for a structural transition towards a biobased economy in order to reduce the dependence on fossil-based raw materials (BMEL, 2014). However, the shift towards bio-based raw materials results in a rising demand for biomass which increases pressures on soil resources and raises conflicts of use, for instance with food production. Due to the limited potential of biomass from waste and residues, an additional cultivation of energy crops, i.e. plants which are exclusively grown for bioenergy production, is required (FNR, 2015a). In order to meet its ambitious targets, the *Bioeconomy Strategy* aims for a sustainable intensification of agriculture, while prioritising food security (BMEL, 2014).

With soil being the crucial resource for the bioeconomy, policies are required to ensure that the intensification of energy crop cultivation will not increase soil degradation. As soil is not only essential for biomass production, but also plays an essential role as a non-renewable resource in the provision of several ecosystem services, such as water filtration or carbon sequestration (DOMINATI et al., 2010), its preservation is of both economic and social importance. However, soil functions and corresponding ecosystem services are endangered by a number of degradation processes, such as erosion, decline of organic matter, compaction, contamination and soil sealing (GLÆSNER et al., 2014). Among these processes, the loss of soil by the erosive force of water poses one of the most severe risks to soils in Europe (PANAGOS et al., 2015a). Even though soil erosion by water is a natural process, influenced by environmental factors such as rainfall erosivity, slope gradient and soil properties, it is accelerated by human agricultural activities. Due to the displacement of large amounts of the most fertile top soil layer, soil erosion negatively affects most soil functions as well as many related ecosystem services (STOLTE et al., 2015). Environmental policies are a tool to ensure sustainable energy crop cultivation by considering both environmental conditions and soil management factors. However, current policies do not sufficiently reflect the multifunctionality of soils and their importance for the bioeconomy (KUTTER et al., 2011; STOLTE et al., 2015; PALEARI, 2017; GLÆSNER et al., 2014) and only few policies directly address erosion by water as a soil threat. As the *Bioeconomy Strategy* is a driver of additional pressures on the state of soils with corresponding impacts on soil functions, policy instruments for soil governance gain increasing importance (JUERGES & HANSJÜRGENS, 2018). In the light of the anticipated challenges of sustainably increasing biomass production, the *National Strategy* suggests further research on soil functions and measures for soil conservation. As a result, the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) launched the funding initiative "soil as a sustainable resource for the bioeconomy" (BonaRes) (BMEL, 2016).

Within the scope of the BonaRes programme, the focus of this study lies on policy instruments for a sustainable use of soil resources in anticipation of an expansion of energy crop cultivation for the bioeconomy. This master's thesis seeks **to evaluate the suitability of existing legislation to ensure sustainable energy crop production and to give recommendations**

for an adjustment of policy instruments with regard to erosion control. Soil erosion by water is taken as an indicator for soil degradation and hence, sustainable agricultural production is assessed here based on preventative measures for erosion control. Based on a comprehensive **literature study**, different aspects of bioenergy production and soil as a resource in the bioeconomy are explored (Chapter 2). After explaining relevant materials and methods (Chapter 3), a **DPSIR Framework** applied to soil erosion is introduced as the conceptual framework of this study (Chapter 4). Based on a **policy analysis** of relevant legislation at EU, national and regional level, effectiveness of erosion control policies is evaluated according to three aspects: targets and degree of legal force, implementation practices at the regional level and control and enforcement schemes (Chapter 5). Furthermore, erosion risk assessment at regional level is examined in a **GIS analysis** of the German federal state Saxony. The environmental pressures of selected energy crops are reviewed and summarised with regard to their potential effect on soil erosion. Moreover, anthropogenic and environmental factors influencing natural soil resistance to erosion are considered alongside corresponding mitigation strategies in soil management (Chapter 6). Finally, the findings are used to identify shortcomings in current legislation to meet the objective of a sustainable supply of biomass feedstock. Within the framework of an **ecological risk analysis** an approach for a more differentiated consideration of local factors is presented (Chapter 7).

2 Background

2.1 Bioeconomy and Bioenergy Production

2.1.1 Political Concept

The concept of a "bioeconomy" was adopted by the European Union (EU) as a strategy to promote the use of renewable biological resources across most economic sectors as a means to respond to global trends such as a growing world population and a changing climate. According to the European Commission, bioeconomy refers to "the production of renewable biological resources and their conversion into food, feed, bio-based products and bioenergy" (EUROPEAN COMMISSION, 2012). The term "knowledge-based economy" (BMBF, 2014) refers to resource use efficiency and the development of new biotechnological and microbiological processes and is used synonymously with "bioeconomy" and "bio-based economy".

The transition towards a bio-based economy offers an alternative to the dependence on finite fossil resources that are depleted by a rising number of people with increasing demands for standards of living and consumption. Furthermore, the substitution of renewable resources for fossil fuels contributes to the decarbonisation of economy and hence, follows the objective of tackling climate change (BMEL, 2014).

However, the replacement of fossil raw materials by biological resources is based on natural assets such as air, soil, water and ecosystems which entails the risk of unsustainable exploitation and conflicts with prevailing uses. In anticipation of potential conflicts, the BMBF incorporated the objective of sustainable use of renewable resources in its first *National Research Strategy BioEconomy 2030* (BMBF, 2010). Also the European Commission's strategy paper *Innovating for Sustainable Growth. A Bioeconomy for Europe* (EUROPEAN COMMISSION, 2012), which was followed by the German *National Policy Strategy Bioeconomy* (BMEL, 2014), refers to the bioeconomy as a "circular economy". With regard to biomass production this requires the sustainable use of natural resources without compromising soil fertility, water balance or climate protection. As land is a limited resource and hence, the cultivation of plants as a raw material for industrial or energetic use might compete with food production, the *National Policy Strategy's* guiding principles clearly prioritise food security over biomass production (BMEL, 2014).

2.1.2 Bioenergy Targets

As the bioeconomy aims for the substitution of fossil resources, the production of bioenergy is one of its main objectives (BMBF, 2010). The raw material for bioenergy is biomass, defined as all phytomass and zoomass which is not fossilised yet as well as all resulting residues thereof and by-products of its use in technical processes (KALTSCHMITT et al., 2009). Compared to other renewable energy sources such as sun or wind, biomass is extremely versatile: it can be used for the production of heat, electricity or fuels. Moreover, its energy can be

stored in the form of primary or secondary energy carriers and therefore, it compensates for the fluctuating availability of solar and wind energy. Currently, the share of bioenergy in Germany amounts to 7.4 % of the final primary energy production, with a share of 58.5 % among the renewable energy carriers (FNR, 2017). According to the Agency for Renewable Resources (FNR) plants which are cultivated for bioenergy production – also called "energy crops" – account for nearly half of biomass used for energy production (45 %), whereas the larger proportion derives from residues such as straw, organic waste, manure and industrial residues. In 2016 the share of energy derived from biomass amounts to 4.7 % in the transport sector, 13.4 % in heat supply and 8 % in electricity production (FNR, 2017).

In the context of the "energy transition" ("Energiewende"), the German Government aims for a reduction of primary energy use by 50% in 2050 (BMWV, 2016). Furthermore, the expected share of bioenergy in this scenario increases to 1915 peta joule (PJ), whereas bioenergy currently merely covers 985 PJ (FNR, 2015b). The FNR estimates that the unused potential of biomass from waste and residues amounts to 30.9 mio. tons of dry matter (DM). Even though this unused potential could double the amount of 26.9 mio. tons of DM of residues which currently contribute 448 PJ of bioenergy (FNR, 2015a), the 2050-scenario still requires an additional amount of 482 PJ to meet the target of 1915 PJ.

However, against the background of a current primary energy demand in Germany of 13 383 PJ in 2016 (FNR, 2017) this theoretical unused potential could contribute max. 3.3 %. In order to achieve the short-term target of 18 % of renewables in primary energy supply in 2020 and at least 35 % of renewables in electricity generation (FNR, 2017), a significant increase of the share of bioenergy is necessary. Furthermore, it can be expected that at the moment due to legal restrictions and logistic challenges not all residues can be used for bioenergy production (FNR, 2015a). As a result, the most flexible and rapid increase of bioenergy can be achieved by the expansion of energy crop cultivation.

2.1.3 Biomass Sources

According to the *Evaluation and Progress Report 2016* by the Federal Office for Agriculture and Food (BLE) the main energy crops of German origin used for biofuel production are maize, rapeseed, sugar beet, wheat, barley, rye and triticale (BLE, 2017). Even though Germany provides the largest proportion of biomass for biofuel production in the EU, it also imports biomass – mainly palm oil from Asia and sugar cane from Central America as well as wastes and residues from all continents – for its bioenergy production (FNR, 2015b). As a result of new regulations for biofuels, producers currently aim for lower greenhouse gas (GHG) emission values and hence, due to their favourable properties, the shares of palm oil and sugar cane increased significantly over the last three years.

Among energy crops from domestic cultivation, winter rapeseed contributes the largest share of starting materials used in biodiesel production, whereas bioethanol mainly relies on

winter wheat and winter rye and partly on sugar beet (BUNZEL et al., 2014). In 2016 5.1 % of energy used in transport sector was provided by renewable resources (FNR, 2017). Among renewable energies in transportation, biodiesel accounted for 62.3 %, whereas bioethanol had a share of only 25.8 %, which makes rapeseed the most important biomass feedstock for biofuels in Germany (BLE, 2017).

While agricultural residues and arable crops play a major role in biofuel production, renewable energy for the heat sector is dominated by solid biomass, primarily wood and woody residues. In 2016 wood contributed 70 % to heat generation from renewables and 9 % to the overall German heat supply (AEE, 2017). Although most wood used for heat generation is waste wood from forest management or wood processing industries, an increasing proportion originates from short-rotation coppices (BMBF, 2014). In these plantations on agricultural land fast-growing wood - mainly poplar or willow trees - is grown in a perennial system. As these trees are grown for the purpose of biomass production for bioenergy generation, short-rotation coppice is hereinafter included in the term "energy crops".

The share of energy crops used for bioenergy generation in biogas plants in 2016 amounts to approx. 50 % of the substrate in terms of mass content and mainly consists of maize (73 %) and grass silage (12 %) (FNR, 2017). Furthermore, manure contributes about 40 % of substrates in biogas plants also in terms of mass content. However, due to the higher energy content of energy crops, they account for approx. 80 % of the energy supply, whereas only approx. 10 % of the generated energy results from manure (FRITSCHKE et al., 2015).

2.1.4 Environmental Concerns

Land-use Conflicts

The political *Bioeconomy Strategy* and the corresponding promotion of biomass production resulted in direct and indirect impacts on the local environment. The most obvious impact is the increasing amount of agricultural land that is used for energy crop cultivation. Within ten years the cultivation area for plants for energetic or industrial use in Germany increased from 1 600 000 ha in 2006 to approx. 2 600 000 ha in 2016. However, out of approx. 16.78 mio. ha of agricultural land in Germany only 14.4 % are used for energy crop cultivation, whereas more than 50 % of the agricultural land area is currently used for fodder production (FNR, 2017).

As a general challenge, energy crop cultivation inevitably leads to conflicts for land in the two main scenarios: First, the conflict for land in the biomass for bioenergy consuming country; if the bioenergy consuming country is growing the required biomass on its own land, this leads to a direct competition with former forms of crop cultivation for food or fodder and is contrary to the principle of prioritising food security. Second, the demand for biomass for bioenergy production also leads to conflicts for land in other countries which do not consume bioenergy; some energy crops such as palm oil or sugar cane cannot be grown in most countries with a political bioenergy-programme and therefore need to be imported. If the biomass-producing country is not the consumer of bioenergy from biomass, the energy crop fields also compete with local food production. Third, countries which are neither consumers nor producers of energy crops might be affected due to an increase of food or

fodder production for exports to biomass for bioenergy producing countries.

These conflicts for land are tackled in different ways. The politically promoted approach aims for the use of abandoned or marginal land rather than agricultural land, while avoiding areas designated for nature conservation, settlement and infrastructure development in order to prevent conflicts for land with other uses. Despite the political target to focus bioenergy production on more disadvantaged areas (BMELV, 2010), in reality most energy crops are grown on fertile, agricultural land (DON et al., 2011).

Another approach to increase the amount of available agricultural land is land-use change. If existing land-use forms are directly converted into cropland for bioenergy production, this process can be relatively easily documented. However, the German Environment Agency (UBA) argues that most land-use changes that are induced by German demands for biomass occur abroad (JERING et al., 2013). Imports of biomass for energy generation such as palm oil lead to a conversion of forests with devastating effects for the local environment (FIELDSEND & SINGH, 2013). Furthermore, bioenergy production triggers indirect land-use changes (iLUC) as a result of increasing demands for food or fodder due to the displacement of these crops by energy crops (BERNDES et al., 2012). The internalisation of land-use change effects is subject to several studies on governance of bioenergy production (GAWEL & LUDWIG, 2011; DON et al., 2011; BOWYER, 2010). However, land-use changes that are related to bioenergy production are difficult to quantify as bioenergy is only one among several drivers (GAWEL & LUDWIG, 2011).

According to the *National Policy Strategy Bioeconomy*, spatial expansions of energy crop cultivation and consequently, land-use conflicts should be prevented by an increase of productivity in terms of yield per hectare. The strategy is referring to continuous enhancements due to technological progress concerning fertilisers, pest control and advanced plant breeding, while soil quality is maintained and enhanced (BMEL, 2014). In practice, this approach and the requirement of economic viability led to an intensification of energy crop cultivation in Germany. As a result of fluctuating market prices and only temporary subsidies just a limited range of crop plants is economically profitable and therefore, energy crop cultivation in Germany is characterised by a small number of plant species grown in large monocultures. Currently, maize cultivation for biogas production in Germany alone requires approx. 1 mio. ha of arable land (FNR, 2017). This development has been discussed in the media in the context of the disappearance of diverse landscape structures and among politicians for its implications for biodiversity and nature conservation (FIELDSEND & SINGH, 2013; BMELV, 2010).

Intensification, land-use change and the cultivation of energy crops on so-called marginal or abandoned land have significant impacts on the immediate environment. Several studies correlate energy crop cultivation with a decline of biodiversity as a result of high pesticide and herbicide uses in monotonous farming systems (BUNZEL et al., 2014; EGGERS et al., 2009) and also establish a link to several forms of land degradation, such as soil erosion, nutrient leaching and environmental pollution due to pesticide leaching (GREIFF et al., 2010; SINGH,

2013; DVL & NABU, 2007; SCHLEGEL et al., 2005). Due to the the increasing specialisation of pests and a high susceptibility to diseases, some crops such as rapeseed cannot be grown in monocultures without high applications of pesticides (BUNZEL et al., 2014). It can be expected that in the long run energy crops grown in monocultures lead to the same adverse effects that have been found for food crops cultivated in continuous monoculture farming systems: due to the lack of structural elements in the landscape and reduced crop diversity a decline in the overall biodiversity leads to a reduction of natural biocontrol and sometimes even to an increase of specialised pathogens and pests (LANDIS et al., 2008; STEWART & CROMEY, 2011). In order to maintain high yields and economic feasibility, the dependence on external inputs such as chemical pesticides, herbicides and fertiliser increases while adjacent water bodies and local biodiversity suffer from run-offs and leaching of chemicals (TILMAN et al., 2002; ZEGADA-LIZARAZU & MONTI, 2011; FIELDSEND & SINGH, 2013).

Biomass Production System

The severity of environmental impacts highly depends on both local factors and the choice of cultivated energy crop; e.g. energy crops such as maize or sugar cane are water intensive and might deplete scarce local water resources which can have adverse effects on regional food production and ecosystems (FIELDSEND & SINGH, 2013). Furthermore, additional environmental concerns result from the plant-specific farming methods.

The most intensive form of agriculture is the cultivation of **row crops**, such as maize, soybean, wheat or rapeseed. When they are grown on fertile agricultural land in an industrialised farming system, they produce high yields and therefore provide the highest economic viability. The systematic row pattern can exacerbate surface run-off of nutrients, pesticides and herbicides as well as the local erosion risk, especially in slope locations (FIELDSEND & SINGH, 2013; ZEGADA-LIZARAZU & MONTI, 2011). As **plantation farming** systems are mainly used for oil palm and sugarcane cultivation, the corresponding environmental impacts occur in the global south rather than in the bioenergy-consuming western countries. Due to high levels of biodiversity in tropical rainforests that typically grow in the same climate zone, biofuel production induced land-use change can lead to high loss rates of local biodiversity in the biomass producing countries (FIELDSEND & SINGH, 2013). Even though plantations can also provide habitats for a variety of species, the dominating monocultures as well as regular disturbance due to harvesting and replanting nevertheless diminish biodiversity significantly compared to biodiversity of natural forests (FIELDSEND & SINGH, 2013).

Due to the objective of using rather marginal land for bioenergy production, alternative biofuel feedstocks such as grasses and short-rotation coppices gain increasingly more attention. Furthermore, the extraction of agricultural residues becomes more economically viable. C₄ grasses such as miscanthus x giganteus or switchgrass have high water use efficiency and also higher conversion rates of light into biomass than C₃ plants such as wheat or rye (CARROLL & SOMERVILLE, 2009; SCHORLING et al., 2014). Also short-rotation plantations can provide high amounts of biomass over growth periods of normally 2 to 5 years (NABU & PARTNER, 2015). Currently, the most common tree species that are grown in plantation systems in Central Europe are poplars and willows (KALTSCHMITT et al., 2009). Both grasses

as well as fast-growing woods are grown in perennial systems and therefore contribute to soil protection through reduced soil disturbance, increased carbon sequestration and avoided soil erosion. Furthermore, adverse environmental effects such as nutrient leaching and pesticide run-off are also reduced due to extensive root systems and continuous vegetation cover (CARROLL & SOMERVILLE, 2009). As short-rotation coppices normally require low fertiliser inputs and no herbicide applications after the second year, adverse environmental impacts are comparatively low (KALTSCHMITT et al., 2009). Nevertheless, biodiversity in a short-rotation coppice environment is significantly lower compared to a forest. Bioenergy production from agricultural residues, wood wastes and manure has been identified by the Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture (BMEL) in Germany's first *Biomass Action Plan* as a promising approach to avoid conflicts for land and to improve bioenergy's GHG-emission balance (BMELV, 2010).

Energy Balance

In light of the bioeconomy's aspiration to reduce GHG emissions by bioenergy use, approaches to account for GHG emissions in the bioenergy production life cycle are highly relevant. With regard to land-use change resulting from energy crop cultivation, most of the converted areas used to be forests, grassland or wetland and hence, acted as carbon sinks. Consequently, their conversion as a result of energy crop cultivation necessarily affects the overall carbon balance of the generated bioenergy. As fertiliser application and the use of agricultural machines cause GHG emission, too, DON et al. (2011) argue for the incorporation of agriculture-related GHG emissions in the carbon footprint of energy crops and conclude that C-losses from land use change even might counterbalance the GHG savings of bioenergy. This has also been assessed on the European level; in an attempt to model GHG emissions caused by indirect land use change associated with the increased use of biofuels and bioliquids in the EU, BOWYER (2010) found that the overall GHG emissions from biofuels might even exceed emissions of equivalent fossil fuel use. The debate on calculation methods of actual GHG emissions resulting from bioenergy production is also of political interest: Currently, this controversy is addressed by targets for biofuel GHG emission reduction of at least 60 % by 2018, i.e. max. 33.5 g CO₂ equivalents per megajoule (CO_{2eq}/MJ), compared to 83.8 g CO_{2eq}/MJ emissions caused by fossil fuels (BLE, 2010). In order to be able to assess the actual emission reductions achieved by biofuels, additional GHG emissions e.g. from land-use change can play a decisive role. Finally, the potential contribution of energy crops to mitigating climate change depends on the amount of GHG released during their production relative to fossil fuels GHG emissions of equivalent energy values.

Sustainability Aspects

The debate on the real contribution of bioenergy to climate change mitigation and implications for the environment led to critical comments as well as diverging opinions on how to proceed towards a bioeconomy.

The UBA argues that any further expansion of German energy crop cultivation is not advisable due to the low area efficiency of local bioenergy production and adverse environmental impacts resulting from conflicts for fertile, agricultural land (JERING et al., 2013). This percep-

tion also influenced the political agenda and led to a shift of focus towards energetic uses of biomass from residues and wood. However, besides the decision to continue political support for short-rotation coppices, research on energy crops receives further funding with the aim of diversifying substrates for biogas plants (BMEL, 2014). Despite the growing attention for sustainability considerations with regard to energy crop cultivation, the ambitious political targets of raising the share of renewables in primary energy consumption to 30 % until 2030 while reducing GHG emissions by at least 55 % rely on the contribution of the biomass sector (BMWI, 2016). Consequently, several studies assess the potential agricultural area that could be used for non-food biomass production without compromising the current self-sufficiency rate. As early as in 2007 the German Advisory Council on the Environment (SRU) stated that in consideration of nature conservation requirements an expansion of the energy crop cultivation area to 3 to 4 mio. ha until 2030 would be possible (SRU, 2007). According to the Renewable Energies Agency's (AEE) review of several studies, potential cultivation areas range from 3 to 5.5 mio ha (AEE, 2013). Also the *National Biomass Action Plan* expects a potential area of approx. 4 mio. ha to be available to energetic biomass production, i.e. 23.8 % of the agricultural area in Germany (BMELV, 2010).

The controversy that bioenergy-related GHG-emissions might outweigh positive impacts of reduced GHG emissions challenges one of the major motivations for implementing the bioeconomy. As tackling climate change is one of the main objectives besides aiming for energy security, it is difficult to justify compromising on biodiversity and nature conservation interests if GHG emissions rise at the same time. However, as all studies comparing life-cycle assessments of energy carriers are based on estimates it is very difficult to make reliable statements on "real" GHG emissions of both biofuels and fossil fuels. Furthermore, it seems questionable that the negative environmental impacts of bioenergy production exceed those of fossil fuel extraction if all long-term effects are taken into account. Estimating the carbon balance of energy carriers is nevertheless an important and necessary method to identify those fuels with the lowest environmental footprint. In order to account for environmental repercussions in other countries resulting from German energy policies, the iLUC-factor has been developed for incorporation of indirect land use change impacts in biofuel assessments (JERING et al., 2013). As part of new sustainability criteria, the EU calls for measures to avoid indirect land-use changes due to biofuel production (DIRECTIVE (EU)2015/1513, 2015). However, the full internalisation of economic and environmental costs of imported biomass is increasingly difficult the bigger the production life cycle and the greater the distance to the producing country. These challenges can be addressed by the promotion of sustainable local bioenergy production while minimising bioenergy-induced land-use changes.

2.2 Legal Background

As German law regulates energy supply from renewable resources by sector, the promotion and standards for bioenergy are addressed in various legal regulations. Since the decision

to complete the phase-out of nuclear energy in Germany by 2022, the aim of increasing the share of renewable energy has been accompanied by ambitious goals for both a reduction of primary energy consumption by 50 % and a reduction of GHG emissions by 80-95 % in 2050 (BMWI, 2016).

In order to contribute to the protection of climate and environment, the *Renewable Energy Sources Act* (EEG) facilitates the development of more sustainable energy supply options and aims for the reduction of economic costs while incorporating external long-term effects (§1 EEG 2017). The EEG sets targets for electricity production from renewable resources and offers fixed payments according to the amount of kWh of renewable electricity input to the national grid. After several revisions since 2000, the most recent version from 2017 formulates the objective of increasing the share of electricity generated by renewable energy to 40-45 % by 2025 and a long-term target of 55-60 % by 2035 and even 80 % by 2050 (§1 EEG 2017). Furthermore, these goals respond to the national targets set by the *EU Renewable Energy Directive*, which requires Germany to increase its share of renewable energy in gross final energy consumption to 18 % by 2020 (DIRECTIVE 2009/28/EC, 2009: An. I). However, the continuous investment in energy generation from biomass that has been triggered by the political instrument of feed-in tariffs led to significant increases in bioenergy and has slowed down after the reduction of remuneration in the latest amendment of the EEG (SCHEFTELOWITZ et al., 2018).

In order to increase shares of renewable energy in the heat sector, the *Renewable Energy Heat Act* (EEWärmeG) aims for covering at least 14 % of buildings' heat and cooling energy demand with renewable energy sources by 2020 (§1 EEWärmeG). For newly constructed buildings that are supplied with biogas, it is supposed to provide at least a share 30 % of their energy demand, whereas the use of solid or liquid biomass as energy sources is to cover at least 50 % of the overall building's energy consumption (§5 EEWärmeG). Evaluating outcomes of Germany's recent energy policies, SCHEFTELOWITZ et al. (2018) identified the rising use of co-processed heat as an indicator of enhanced energy efficiency.

In the context of the EU decarbonisation strategy, Germany replaced quotas for biofuels by targets for the reduction of GHG emissions of fuels in the transport sector. According to *Federal Immission Control Act* (BImSchG) transport-related GHG emissions are to be reduced by 6 % in 2020 (§37a BImSchG).

In order to ensure quality and sustainability of bioenergy provision, renewable energy policies also set standards for environmental requirements in biomass production as well as for the composition of biofuels. In accordance to KALTSCHMITT et al. (2009), biomass is defined in the *Biomass Ordinance* (BiomasseV) as plants and plant parts as well as energy carriers produced thereof – including biogas and alcohols –, wastes and by-products of plant or animal origin (§2 BiomasseV). The sustainability criteria for the production of electricity from biomass are defined in the *Biomass Electricity Sustainability Ordinance* (BioSt-NachV). Accordingly, bioenergy is only remunerated as stated in the EEG 2017 if it was not produced at the expense of nature conservation areas or carbon sinks while complying with the standards defined as *Good Agricultural and Environmental Condition* (GAEC) (§§4-7 BioSt-NachV).

Furthermore, the BioSt-NachV requires liquid biomass used for electricity generation to have a GHG reduction potential of at least 50 %, which has been raised to 60 % in 2018 for those plants that started to operate after 2016 (§8 BioSt-NachV). The GHG reduction is calculated against the reference value of 91 g CO_{2eq}/MJ emitted during electricity generation by fossil fuels, while the reference value is 85 g CO_{2eq}/MJ if biomass is used in a cogeneration system (Annex I, BioSt-NachV). In line with amendments to the *EU Renewable Energy Directive 2009/28/EC* by DIRECTIVE (EU)2015/1513 (2015), which also considers impacts of indirect land-use change induced by biofuel production, similar sustainability criteria are formulated. Besides the same requirements with regard to nature conservation, preservation of carbon sinks and compliance with GAEC, the *Biofuel Sustainability Ordinance* (Biokraft-NachV) aims for a reduction of GHG by 50-60 % – depending on the plants' start of operation (§§4-8 Biokraft-NachV). However, the reference value for fossil fuel emissions for equivalent energy generation is set to 83.8 g CO_{2eq}/MJ (§37a BimSchG). The objective of a GHG-reduction rate in the heat sector also amounts to a reduction of at least 50 % from 2017 and at least 60 % as defined by §8 BioSt-NachV, which is calculated against the equivalent of 77 g CO_{2eq}/MJ for liquid biomass or against 85 g CO_{2eq}/MJ if used in a cogeneration system (EEWärmeG). For solid biomass a conversion efficiency of at least 70 % is required (EEWärmeG).

2.3 Soil as a Resource

2.3.1 Soil in the Bioeconomy

As the main fuel in the bioeconomy is biomass, agricultural fields, grassland and forests act as its production systems (BMBF, 2014). Soil plays a fundamental role for the functionality of these ecosystems and hence, soil is framed as an essential resource and the decisive factor for progress in the transformation of our economy. To provide incentives for research on sustainable biomass production, the BMBF provides funding-support for the programme *Soil as a sustainable resource for the bioeconomy – BonaRes* (BMEL, 2016).

Besides providing food and raw materials, soils perform various other so-called ecosystem services. As defined by DOMINATI et al. (2010), ecosystem services directly affect human well-being and therefore services related to securing the production of food and raw materials, such as flood mitigation, nutrient filtration, biological control of pests and diseases as well as recycling of wastes and carbon sequestration are also attributed to soils. Furthermore, soil formation and maintenance depend on even more fundamental processes like nutrient and water cycling and soil biological activity (DOMINATI et al., 2010). Besides these physical properties soils also provide cultural services due to their importance for recreation, aesthetics, identity and religious rites (JÓNSSON & DAVÍÐSDÓTTIR, 2016). The *Bioeconomy Strategy* acknowledges the importance of soil and aims in its objectives for a sustainable use of renewable resources while maintaining biodiversity and soil fertility (BMEL, 2014). Due to the crucial contributions of soils to the functionality of other ecosystems, maintaining and enhancing soil quality are essential measures for achieving a sustainable biomass production (OLSON et al., 2017).

As a result of human activities in various economic sectors, but also due to climate change, a growing area in Europe is exposed to degradation processes that lead to a reduction of soil ecosystem service provision (PANAGOS et al., 2015a). Even though geological factors, topography and climate determine soils' vulnerability to most degradation processes, anthropogenic land management plays a role of increasing importance. Directly linked to urban sprawl, soil sealing in Germany leads to an increase of land-take for housing and transport of about 81 ha per day (UBA, 2015). Also contamination with organic and anorganic pollutants mostly derives from human activities; while most heavy metal emissions are declining, zinc and copper emissions increased by more than 30 % over the last twenty years. Agriculture is one of the main drivers of soil pollution related to application of manure and sewage sludge to fields. Due to soils' buffer and filter functions, contaminants can be accumulated in soils and pose a risk to the quality of agricultural products. Miscalculated fertiliser applications as well as the deposition of air-borne particles can lead to soil acidification, eutrophication of surface waters and also endanger local ground water resources. The current average surplus of nitrate inputs on fields in Germany still amounts to 95 kg/ha (UBA, 2014). Other results from unsustainable land management are soil compaction and declining soil organic matter contents, which lead to a reduction of soil fertility and biodiversity (UBA, 2015). The use of heavy machinery on the fields and land-use change can have adverse effects on soil productivity, while erosion processes reduce the actual amounts of available soil. Erosion of the upper soil layers by wind or water can lead to a quick degradation of the fertile topsoil with corresponding impacts on yields and ecosystem services. In 2012 soil fertility of 2049 mio. ha - in total 17 % - of arable land in Germany was endangered by erosion (MAL et al., 2015). Most endangered areas were affected by soil erosion by water (15 %), whereas only 2.3 % of arable land were exposed to high wind erosion risks.

It can be assumed that the implementation of the bioeconomy's objectives increases the demand for biomass as well as the pressure on German land resources. In the concept of the bioeconomy the conflict for land is addressed by an increase of yield per hectare, which requires more artificial inputs and hence, leads to an intensification of farming practices (BMEL, 2014). Intensive farming methods with regard to tillage practices, weed management and choice of cultivated crops are known to have adverse effects on soil ecosystem services as well as on soil stability in regions prone to soil erosion (OLSON et al., 2017).

2.3.2 Soil Erosion Risk

In general soil erosion refers to the detachment, transport and disposition, i.e. the relocation of soil particles by either wind or water (STOLTE et al., 2015). Soil erosion by water is considered as one of the most severe soil threats as its process is the cause for the greatest loss of soil (PANAGOS et al., 2015a). Although soil erosion is a natural process influenced by geomorphological and climatic factors, it is significantly exacerbated by human activities which led to an acceleration of soil degradation during recent decades (DEUMLICH et al., 2006). Unlike slope characteristics, soil properties and precipitation erosivity, soil management such as tillage practices can be influenced and adjusted to local environmental conditions (PANAGOS et al., 2016). Falling raindrops detach soil particles, which is defined as

rainsplash erosion, whereas running water causes either erosion on large parts of the surface (interill or sheet erosion) or forms channels (rill erosion) that might expand to so-called erosion gullies (STOLTE et al., 2015). As sheet and rill erosion can detach and transport large amounts of soil particles which are accumulated at the bottom of the slope, these erosion forms can also cause adverse off-site effects. The highest erosion risk is attributed to steep slopes in areas with high amounts of rainfall. However, even a gradient of 2 % can lead to soil erosion by water (LABO, 2017). Furthermore, vegetation cover reduces the risk, whereas tillage – especially ploughing transversely to contour lines – leads to an increase of the erosion risk. BERENDSE et al. (2015) found that a decline in plant species diversity also increases soil loss rates and conclude that diversifying plant communities on slopes can contribute to erosion control.

The removal of the upper soil layer leads to a decline of soil fertility and related ecosystem services such as food provision. However, also the underlying soil services like filtration of pollutants and nutrients as well as water retention are negatively affected. In an attempt to calculate the direct costs of annual soil loss and related crop productivity due to water erosion in the EU, PANAGOS et al. (2018) estimate related costs of € 300 mio. in the agricultural sector and a loss of € 155 mio. loss in GDP. However, not only the total loss, but also the time scale of soil degradation is relevant. Gradual erosion over a longer period leads to a reduction of plant available nutrients and organic matter that is slowly compensated for, whereas the sudden removal of a large proportion of the topsoil layer significantly affects the soil's fertility with corresponding implications for harvest yields (GOVERS et al., 2004). Besides on-site effects, water erosion can have adverse off-site effects in the area of sediment deposition. Not only soil particles but also nutrients and potentially contaminants are transported and might harm other ecosystems, while polluting surface water bodies (SYRBE et al., 2017). By exceeding the soil's and vegetation's water retention capacity, surface run-off contributes to local flood risk. Consequently, SYRBE et al. (2017) and MARKOV & NEDKOV (2016) identify erosion regulation as an ecosystem service that is provided by soils and can be mainly influenced by land management practices and corresponding vegetation cover.

In their assessment of annual soil erosion rates by water in the EU, using the Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation (RUSLE) model PANAGOS et al. (2015a) estimate a mean soil loss rate of 2.46 t/ha yr and a total annual soil loss of 970 Mt. For Germany they calculate a loss of 1.25 t of soil per hectare and year (PANAGOS et al., 2015a). In their comparison of several studies on soil erosion risk assessments in European countries, STOLTE et al. (2015) compile estimated soil loss rates for Germany ranging from 0.9 to 2.7 t/ha yr. In most assessments German soil loss rates remain below 2 t/ha yr which is widely considered as sustainable. However, VERHEIJEN et al. (2009) suggest that by applying the precautionary principle, tolerable soil erosion rates in Europe should be limited to 1.4 t/ha yr. Taking European soil formation rates of 0.3 to ca. 1.2 t/ha yr into account, the identified tolerable erosion rates could be compensated for by weathering and deposition processes (VERHEIJEN et al., 2009). For local soil conservation also variations within the average soil loss rates

are relevant. In sparsely vegetated areas soil loss rates amount to > 40 t/ha yr, whereas forests show loss rates of merely 0.07 t/ha yr (PANAGOS et al., 2015a). As a result of climate change soil erosion risks are expected to increase due to effects of rising temperatures on vegetation periods. According to WURBS & STEININGER (2011) changes in seasonality of vegetation cover might increase the erosion risk by 10 % until 2040 and even by 25 % afterwards. Furthermore, seasonal variability of extreme weather events such as heavy precipitation is expected to increase as well as precipitation sums in spring, autumn and summer (LABO, 2017).

2.3.3 Soil Erosion Control

Current soil loss rates and the prospect of more extreme weather events with the corresponding implications for soil erosion necessitate the implementation of measures for erosion control. As most soil erosion by water occurs on agricultural fields (PANAGOS et al., 2015a), strategies focus on adjusting farming practices and taking precautionary measures before soil erosion occurs. In Germany the *Good Agricultural Practice* in cultivation methods and soil conservation aims for a permanent soil cover and stable soil structures. In order to prevent the detachment of soil particles by water measures intend to increase soils infiltration and water retention capacities by reducing or abandoning tillage farming practices (AID, 2015). However, CARR et al. (2011) discuss the disadvantages of no-till farming practice with regard to weed control, which might lead to an increase in synthetic herbicide application. Especially in organic farming giving up tillage practices poses a challenge and makes a transition to reduced tillage more attractive. Furthermore, soil compaction caused by inappropriate use of heavy land machinery is to be avoided due to its adverse effects on soil's infiltration capacity and fertility. Liming and the application of organic substances can enhance soil structure as well as its water retention capacity (LABO, 2017). Covering bare soil with mulch or harvest residues also has a protective effect and therefore reduces the erosion risk significantly (AID, 2015). Intercropping systems and freeze-off catch crops can also be used for closing seasonal gaps in vegetation cover (GRASS et al., 2013).

In order to mitigate adverse effects of soil erosion, strip cultivation parallel to the slope contours as a means for a reduction of slope length as well as landscape structure elements such as hedges or grass strips can prevent down-slope transport of sediments. Establishing riparian strips protects water bodies against the contamination with sediments and agricultural chemicals (LABO, 2017). Furthermore, contour farming, parallel to the slope is recommended as a means to counteract the creation of preferential flow paths. Besides adjusted farming practices, also the choice of cultivated crops plays a role in coping with erosion risks. On fields with high erosion risks it is recommended to grow perennial forage crops instead of row crops such as maize which is known to increase soil erosion (FRIELINGHAUS et al., 2002). In the cultivation of row crops nurse crops can cover the surface of bare soil in between the rows. Moreover, the Federal State Soil Protection Working Group (LABO) recommends the establishment of permanent pastures, forest or set-aside of fields with high erosion risk (LABO, 2017).

Besides the *Code of Good Practice*, the German federal states also provide guidance in the form

of brochures and manuals (FRIELINGHAUS et al., 2002; LFULG, 2016; LUBW, 2011). These leaflets inform on the assessment of erosion risks as well as the legal obligations to report erosion incidents. Furthermore, they provide not only recommendations on measures for a reduction of erosion risks, but also offer concepts for regional erosion control plans with detailed evaluation of current farming methods and recommendations for improvement. The LABO commented on the current legislation and requirements for erosion control according to the *Code of Good Practice* by emphasising the importance of incorporating the local environmental conditions into the development of specific preventive measures, especially for large parcels (LABO, 2014).

In their evaluation of currently applied measures for erosion control the Bavarian State Research Centre for Agriculture (LfL) identifies the shortcoming of implementing only one of the erosion control measures mentioned above. For instance contour farming alone could not prevent soil erosion in maize cultivation due to the lack of vegetation cover in May and June and therefore, a reasonable combination of measures seems advisable (LfL, 2013). However, in their assessment of soil loss by water erosion in Europe, PANAGOS et al. (2015a) draw a positive conclusion regarding the achievements of current European requirements for GAEC. Assuming that hardly any anti-erosion measures were applied before the implementation of the GAEC requirements, the new erosion control policies led to a reduction of soil loss on arable lands by 20.2 % between 2003 and 2010.

3 Materials and Methods

3.1 Policy Analysis

The objective to assess the current state of environmental policy instruments on soil erosion control in Germany is achieved by screening all policy documents that set regulations for erosion control on German soils in agricultural use. Environmental policy instruments are defined according to MICKWITZ (2003: 419) as "the set of techniques by which governmental authorities wield their power in attempting to affect society – in terms of values and beliefs, action and organization – in such a way as to improve, or to prevent the deterioration of, the quality of the natural environment".

As the legal framework for soil erosion control is analysed at different political levels. Firstly, European directives and programmes as well as the implementation thereof at the federal level in addition to national legislation are reviewed and thereafter categorised by their level of legal force. Secondly, the implementation at federal state level is analysed by a screening of federal legislation of three states in Germany – Saxony, Bavaria and Baden-Wuerttemberg. These three have also been chosen as examples for a further evaluation of the consideration of local environmental factors in erosion control policies at regional level. Thirdly, identified policy documents which are relevant to German erosion control regulation are assessed in terms of effectiveness.

The relevant environmental policy instruments are grouped according to the "degree of authoritative force involved", i.e. regulation (mandatory) or economic instruments (incentive-based) (MICKWITZ, 2003). Following the ranking, regulatory instruments comprise legally binding restrictions or standards that are used to limit the freedom of choice of the agents. By giving financial incentives, such as subsidies, taxes or tradeable permits, economic instruments change the costs or benefits of a certain choice for the agents. Economic instruments are voluntary, whereas compliance with standards set by regulatory instruments is mandatory (JUERGES & HANSJÜRGENS, 2018; MICKWITZ, 2003).

The most direct way of assessing the effectiveness of policy instruments is the evaluation of indicators describing the state of the policy objective (WILSON & BULLER, 2001). However, as only few policy instruments address soil conservation directly in their objectives, it is often difficult to deduce effects on soil functions resulting from a specific piece of legislation (PRAGER et al., 2011). Furthermore, the difficulty to collect data on changes in soil processes over time often limits the effectiveness of indicators (WILSON & BULLER, 2001). Soil erosion by water can be either assessed by the soil erosion risk or by the actual amount of soil loss by erosion. Even though farmers are required to report major soil erosion incidents on their fields (LFULG, 2016), it is difficult to derive the overall soil loss per ha and year due to the lack of regular field measurements. Also the Joint Research Centre (JRC) has identified the absence of harmonised measures of soil erosion rates as a problem (JONES et al., 2012). Consequently, both the soil erosion risk and the actual soil loss are assessed by

modelling approaches with varying results (VERHEIJEN et al., 2009). The soil erosion risk is normally calculated based on local environmental factors, such as rainfall, topography and soil structure, whereas the modelled soil loss by water erosion also includes factors concerning soil management practices and soil cover (PANAGOS et al., 2015e).

In the absence of data on changes in soil loss amounts in high temporal and spatial resolutions as well as on corresponding baseline conditions, it is challenging to assess the impacts of existing soil conservation policies. For this reason, effectiveness of policy instruments regarding erosion control is evaluated by their targets, degree of legal force, implementation practices at regional level as well as control and enforcement schemes.

3.2 Soil Loss Equation Models

Several approaches have been developed to simulate erosion and sediment processes, addressing various aspects of sediment transport at different levels of detail and scale. MERRITT et al. (2003) distinguish between empirical, conceptual and physics-based models, out of which empirical models have the lowest degree of complexity and data requirements. Despite some criticism concerning their simplification of reality, the empirical Universal Soil Loss Equation (USLE) model, developed in 1978 by WISCHMEIER & SMITH (1978), is one of the most common soil erosion models. The annual average soil loss rate per hectare is calculated by multiplying environmental factors (topography, soil properties, rainfall) and management-induced factors (erosion control practices, vegetation cover). Although it was developed for calculating annual estimates of soil erosion from hill slopes, it is also used for assessments on catchment and also at regional level (MARKOV & NEDKOV, 2016; GUERRA et al., 2016). In order to make the model more process-based, the Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation (RUSLE) model was proposed: the USLE factors were supplemented by more comprehensive databases, improved regression equations and more subfactors, accounting for seasonal variations, while maintaining the basic format of the equation (RENARD et al., 1997). Especially the level of complexity in factoring in soil coverage is seen as a major advantage of the RUSLE over the USLE (MERRITT et al., 2003). Since its introduction, authors have been adjusting the RUSLE model for their purposes, e.g. by accounting for the impact of run-off on erosion in the modified USLE model (USLE-M) (KINNELL & RISSE, 1998) or by implementing an additional soil stoniness factor in the Extended RUSLE model (e-RUSLE) (BOSCO et al., 2015). In order to calculate the annual soil loss rate by water, the RUSLE considers six factors (PANAGOS et al., 2015e):

$$E = R \cdot K \cdot S \cdot L \cdot C \cdot P \quad (1)$$

where E: average annual soil loss (t /ha yr), R: rainfall erosivity factor (MJ mm /ha h yr), K: soil erodibility factor (t ha h/ ha MJ mm), S: slope steepness factor (dimensionless), L: slope length factor (dimensionless), C: cover-management factor (dimensionless), P: support practice factor (dimensionless).

Despite criticism on simplified assumptions concerning physics and heterogeneity of environmental parameters in empirical models (MERRITT et al., 2003), RUSLE is the most frequently used simulation model for large regions (PANAGOS et al., 2015e). Especially on the European scale, RUSLE is constantly being improved with regard to input layer quality, which is demonstrated in numerous publications by the JRC of the European Commission (PANAGOS et al., 2015a; PANAGOS et al., 2015d; PANAGOS et al., 2015e; PANAGOS et al., 2015c; PANAGOS et al., 2015b; PANAGOS et al., 2014). In Germany, the USLE model was adjusted by SCHWERTMANN et al., 1990 and standardised as ABAG ("Universal Soil Loss Equation in Germany") (DIN19708, 2017). The ABAG recommends a selection of factors relevant for the respective research question. The natural erosion risk (E_{nat}) is a measure of site vulnerability to soil erosion by water based on rainfall erosivity, soil erodibility and slope steepness:

$$E_{\text{nat}} = R \cdot K \cdot S \quad (2)$$

According to the ABAG's categorisation, areas with $E_{\text{nat}} < 0.5 \text{ t /ha yr}$ have "no or very low erosion risk", whereas $> 7.5 \text{ t}$ of soil loss per hectare and year indicate a "high natural erosion risk". In order to assess the full water erosion risk, also management-induced factors, such as soil cover (C), erosion control practices (P) and slope length (L) are taken into account (see eq. 1). Based on this calculation only areas with an annual soil loss $< 0.2 \text{ t/ha}$ are defined as at very low risk of soil erosion, while the classification as areas with high erosion risk starts with soil losses of 3 t /ha yr (DIN19708, 2017).

More details on calculation methods of the respective factors can be found in DIN19708 (in German) or in the respective papers by Panagos et al. (R: PANAGOS et al. (2015a); K: PANAGOS et al. (2014); SL: PANAGOS et al. (2015b); PANAGOS et al. (2015c); P: PANAGOS et al. (2015d)).

3.3 Study Areas

Due to the principle of subsidiarity, the German federal states are in charge of the implementation of erosion control policies. As they have the administrative power to decide how to integrate federal laws in their legislation and which derogations to grant to farmers, erosion control regulations slightly vary between all federal states.

In order to assess the implementation at regional level, three federal states were chosen for an in-depth analysis. After reviewing firstly the geographical distribution of the occurrence of soil erosion by water and secondly data availability, Saxony, Bavaria and Baden-Wuerttemberg were chosen as study areas (Fig.1). The *Institute for Geosciences and Natural Resources* (BGR) identified four focus areas of erosion risk by water out of which three – Saxon Hills with the Saxon Uplands, the Gäu Plateaus and the lower Bavarian Upland – are covered by the study area (BGR, 2014). Besides a screening of the respective federal states' policy documents on erosion control, the local environmental conditions considered in federal state law are examined in a geographical information system (GIS) analysis.

Fig. 1: Study area in eastern and southern Germany: Saxony (SN), Bavaria (BY) and Baden-Wuerttemberg (BW). Overview of potential erosion risk by water on agricultural land according to BGR.

3.4 GIS-Analysis

Local factors play a major role in soil erosion processes (PANAGOS et al., 2015e). In order to justify regulations for soil management in areas prone to soil erosion by water, first the erosion risk is assessed. In Germany it is the task of the federal states to categorise their agricultural fields according to their erosion risk and provide this information to the farmers in the form of a map, the **Erosionskataster** ("Erosion Registry"). The spatial data required for the generation of the Erosionskataster is provided by the competent regional authorities. Following DIN19708 (2017), the potential erosion risk by water takes the soil erodibility factor, the slope steepness factor and optionally also the rainfall erosivity factor and the slope length factor into account. Spatial variance of each factor is represented by a spatial layer in vector or raster data format. By overlaying and multiplying all factors the erosion risk can be calculated. The choice of the number of factors considered is left to the federal states and therefore it also varies between the three federal states in the study area. Due to difficulties with data provision by the responsible federal states, the GIS-analysis is limited to geodata from Saxony. Tab.1 gives an overview of the map layers used by the federal state of Saxony to calculate the potential soil erosion risk by water.

Tab. 1: Data sources used in Saxony for the compilation of an Erosionskataster

Data description	Data source	Application	
Saxony			
Soil map with resolution 1:200 000	Saxon State Office for the Environment, Agriculture and Geology (LfULG) 2012	Derivation of K-factor	Calculation of the erosion risk by water with $K \cdot S \cdot R$ (after DIN19708, 2017)
DEM with a resolution of 20 m	Geoinformation and Land Survey Saxony (GeoSN) 2012	Derivation of S-factor	
Rainfall series of 1952-2004	German Meteorological Service (DWD) 2013	Derivation of R-factor	area unit: Feldblock

The categorisation of erosion risk classes is calculated in accordance with DIN19708 (2017) as required by AgrarZahlVerpflV, annex 2 for the common area units used for plots of land in the respective federal state. The thresholds applied in legislation for "erosion risk" (CC_{wasser1}) and "high erosion risk" (CC_{wasser2}) correspond to the two highest erosion risk classes in DIN19708 (2017) – "very high" and "extremely high erosion risk" – whereas DIN-norm classes "high" to "no erosion risk" are equally classified as "no erosion risk" (CC_{wasser0}) (Tab.2).

Tab. 2: Thresholds used for the assessment of the potential erosion risk by water

Classification according to AgrarZahlVerpflV, annex 2	Product of erosion factors: $K \cdot S$ [in t/ ha yr]	Product of erosion factors: $K \cdot S \cdot R$ [in t/ ha yr]	Classification of erosion risk according to DIN19708, 2017
No risk class (CC_{wasser0})	< 0.3	< 2.5	no risk/very low
		2.5 - < 5	low
		5 - < 7.5	medium
		7.5 - < 15	high
CC_{wasser1}	0.3 - < 0.55	15 - < 27.5	very high
CC_{wasser2}	≥ 0.55	≥ 27.5	extremely high

In addition to the Erosionskataster, the federal states compile an **Erosionsatlas** ("Erosion Atlas") to predict the expected average annual soil loss from agricultural fields in tons per hectare. These risk assessments also take the environmental factors like slope gradient, rainfall erosivity and soil erodibility into account. However, the Erosionsatlas is regularly updated – in Saxony it is based on the more recent rainfall series of 1993-2012, a soil map with the resolution of 1:50 000 (BK50) and a DEM with 5-m-resolution.

In this study the Erosionsatlas represents the most up-to-date assessment of real local conditions available without having available in-situ measurements. In order to assess whether the current implementation of erosion control policies on the regional level takes sufficient account of local environmental conditions, a GIS-analysis is performed. The Erosionskataster results from both federal laws and adjustments made to legislation on the federal state level, whereas the Erosionsatlas displays the most up-to-date assessment of local erosion risk, provided by the regional authorities. Consequently, divergent classifications of erosion risk areas can reveal shortcomings of current legislation to restrict soil management on all areas prone to soil erosion by water.

Fig. 2: Exemplary map sections to demonstrate the generation of a difference map. Erosionsatlas (A) - Erosionskataster (B) = difference map (C).

erision risk classes. Fig.2 demonstrates the generation of a difference map: By subtracting the erosion risk classes according to the Erosionskataster (B) from those classified in the Erosionsatlas (A) a difference map (C) is produced. Areas classified as 0 are identical in both maps, whereas 1 and 2 indicate higher erosion risk classes in the Erosionsatlas compared to those classified according to the Erosionskataster. Negative values reflect higher erosion risk classes in the Erosionskataster than in the Erosionsatlas.

3.5 Ecological Risk Analysis

The Ecological Risk Analysis, originally a regional planning tool, defines the potential risk of environmental impairment by taking spatial or situational variation of two overlaying factors into account (SCHULTZE et al., 2008). For instance, the local potential risk of a certain environmental impact can be assessed in a simple risk matrix (Fig.3), based on local vulnerability and intensity of the impact.

For the display and processing of geodata described above, the open source desktop application QuantumGIS (QGIS), Version 2.12.3, is used. All data is transferred to the European Terrestrial Reference System 1989 (ETRS89) and the Universal Transverse Mercator Coordinate System (UTM) zone 33N (EPSG: 25833). Different scaling in erosion risk classes require a reclassification to have equal thresholds for $CC_{wasser1}$, $CC_{wasser2}$ and $CC_{wasser0}$ classes. The erosion risk from the Erosionsatlas is averaged for the same unit areas used in the Erosionskataster and transferred to a corresponding vector file. The *Statistical Summary Panel* in QGIS facilitates the comparison of area sizes designated to the respective ero-

Fig. 3: Simple risk matrix without weighting, based on SCHULTZE et al., 2008.

PETERS et al. (2010) and SCHULTZE et al. (2008) have adopted the framework of an Ecological Risk Analysis for an evaluation of the impairment of landscape and nature functions in Germany caused by energy crop cultivation. In their risk assessments high vulnerability of a site coinciding with high impact intensity of certain energy crops led to a high potential environmental risk in the respective impact category. In both studies the simple risk matrix was adjusted by a weighting categorisation of potential risks (SCHULTZE et al., 2008; PETERS et al., 2010).

The weighting of impact factors resulted in lower risks for high impact intensities, but low vulnerability at the specific site and also for low impact intensities on highly vulnerable sites (Fig.4, A). However, a weighting in risk matrices can also increase the resulting risk levels by ascribing a high risk to any inter-

Fig. 4: Simple risk matrices with weighting. A: weighting with emphasis on low impacts, resulting in reduced risk potentials; B: weighting with emphasis on high impacts, resulting in increased risk potentials

section of factors with either high vulnerability or high intensity (Fig.4, B). The latter can for instance be used to derive precautionary measures from the risk assessment in order to meet nature conservation objectives (PETERS et al., 2010).

3.6 Data Sources

Geodata

The **Erosionsatlas** is freely available on the website of the Saxon State Office for the Environment, Agriculture and Geology (LfULG). The erosion risk map is based on the K-, S- and R-factor and was downloaded as a raster file. As the **Erosionskataster** comprises detailed information on the categorised erosion risk of specific field units and serves as a baseline

for farmers' applications for subsidies, it is not available online. Upon request, however, the Saxon State Ministry for the Environment and Agriculture (SMUL) kindly provided the registry of 2018 as a shapefile.

Policy Documents

All policy documents, i.e. regulations, directives, decisions, strategy papers and laws, that were reviewed and analysed in this study are freely available on the internet and can be found with the details published in the bibliography.

4 DPSIR Framework Applied to Soil Erosion

Developing policies for soil protection and assessing their impact on soil functions requires insights into both soil science and the functioning of policy instruments. In order to illustrate the interdisciplinary links between these research fields and identify potential feedback loops for the improvement of existing policies, the Driver-Pressure-State-Impact-Response (DPSIR) approach is used as an analytical framework. First developed as a reduced Pressure-State-Response model by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 1993) and later extended by the EEA (SMEETS & WETERINGS, 1999), the DPSIR framework shows the impacts of societal activities on environmental quality as a loop of cause and effect relationships. As an approach to structure causal chains, the framework has been applied to soil issues before (EEA, 2001; GOBIN et al., 2002; GLÆSNER et al., 2014) and was further developed and adjusted in the field of impact assessment (HELMING et al., 2013; HELMING et al., 2018). Here, the DPSIR framework assesses the **pressures** that are exerted by **drivers** (including policies) on the **state** of the soil system. Closing the loop, the identified **impacts** on society are addressed by **responses** in the form of adjustments to existing policies (Fig.5).

Fig. 5: Simple DPSIR framework, based on SMEETS & WETERINGS, 1999. Thin arrows represent feedback loops after first impact assessment

Within the scope of the BonaRes Project, the DPSIR framework is used to highlight the interface between the natural soil system and the socioeconomic system (VOGEL et al., 2018). Following their concept of soil management and soil functions being the crucial links between these two systems, an analytical framework has been developed to reflect the implications of the *Bioeconomy Strategy* on arable soil resources with particular attention to the soil threat of erosion by water (Fig.6).

Driver

According to the ambitious political targets for bioenergy generation, the *Bioeconomy Strategy* is the **driver** aiming for an intensification of soil management (Fig.6, (1)). TECHEN & HELMING (2017) distinguish in their analysis of drivers and trends of soil management in Germany between quantitative and qualitative changes in soil management that exert pressures on the state of the soil system. In order to avoid further land expansion for biomass cultivation for energy, quantitative changes, such as increasing inputs of nutrients, pesticides, herbicides and harvest frequencies, can help achieving higher yields from the same land area. Furthermore, qualitative changes in farming methods, i.e. the choice of crops, rotation frequency, spatial patterns of crop cultivation and mechanical pressures on soil, affect both crop yields and the state of the soil system (TECHEN & HELMING, 2017).

Fig. 6: DPSIR Framework applied to soil erosion in the context of the *Bioeconomy Strategy*, based on VOGEL et al. (2018).

Pressure

Consequently, anthropogenic soil management as part of farming practices can be considered as a **pressure** on arable soil resources. In order to increase biomass production, intensive farming methods comprise intensive tillage practices and crop cultivation in monoculture with high fertiliser, herbicide and pesticide inputs (Fig.6, (2)). However, constant agricultural use with frequent harvests leads to gradual soil degradation and poses a risk to soil fertility (TILMAN et al., 2002). Soil degradation by erosion is one of the main soil threats identified by the EU Commission’s Communication *Towards a Thematic Strategy on Soil Protection* (COM(2006)231, 2002). More sustainable soil management practices comprise reduced or no-tillage practices, more precise fertiliser applications leading to an improvement of nutrient-use efficiency, cover crops, intercropping systems, leaving plant residues on the fields and additional strategies for enhancing soil stability and biodiversity, such as contour farming or grass margins.

State

The identified soil threats jeopardise the **state** of the soil system (Fig.6, (3)). In accordance with the BonaRes DPSIR framework (VOGEL et al., 2018; HELMING et al., 2018), the state of the soil system is determined by functional soil characteristics that result from the interactions between physical, chemical and biological soil processes and soil components. The focus of the DPSIR-Framework lies on the impacts of policies on soils and therefore on the management-induced changes to the state of soils and their functions. However, it

is crucial to take into account that environmental factors, not only soil properties but also topography and climate, can have a significant influence on the degree of impact which is caused by soil management practices (VOGEL et al., 2018). With regard to soil erosion, rainfall erosivity, slope characteristics and soil erodibility, i.e. grain sizes and properties, are the most relevant environmental factors (Fig.6, (A)) (PANAGOS et al., 2015a). The management-induced pressures that are described above can lead to a number of on-site and off-site effects related to the transport of sediment by water as a result of erosion incidents. Tillage practices can not only increase decomposition of soil organic matter (SOM) by microorganisms, leading to a depletion of the sequestered carbon and to carbon dioxide emissions to the atmosphere, but they also destabilise soil aggregates. The most devastating on-site effect is the loss of the upper soil layer, which contains most SOM and therefore also the highest concentration of soil organic carbon (SOC). Due to the SOM property to absorb nutrients that are essential for plant growth and provide food for microorganisms, the composition of the top soil layer has a great influence on soil fertility (OLSON et al., 2017). Besides aggregate stability soil's infiltration capacity is a relevant functional characteristic for the soil resilience to erosion by water. The infiltration capacity depends on a range of soil properties including the SOM content and pore structure, which are also affected by tillage practices. However, despite all adjustments to soil management, slope gradient and rainfall erodibility often determine the severity of the erosion risk and limit farming opportunities in some areas in terms of yields and range of suitable crops.

Off-site impacts of erosion by water are related to the sedimentation of transported material. In spite of the positive properties of the fertile upper soil layer, its accumulation can lead to compaction and disturbs the in-situ soil layering. Furthermore, negative impacts on infrastructure at spatial scales much larger than the cultivated plots receive increasing attention (VALENTIN et al., 2005). Not only artificial structures such as roads or drainage systems can be affected, but also other environmental media. Emissions to adjacent water bodies can lead to a decline in water quality – especially if the soil material contains high concentrations of pesticides, herbicides or nutrients causing water stress or eutrophication (GOBIN et al., 2002).

Impacts

Pressures from soil management practices on functional soil characteristics have an **impact** on soil functions (Fig.6, (4)). Even though the term "soil functions" is sometimes used synonymously with "ecosystem services" (SCHWILCH et al., 2016), in this DPSIR framework these two terms reflect two different perceptions of soil from the view of the socioeconomic and the soil system. Following the approach of VOGEL et al. (2018), ecosystem services are defined in the context of an anthropogenic valuation system that considers contributions of soil resources to human well-being, whereas soil functions emerge from natural processes in the soil system. Consequently, as soil functions are influenced by changes in functional soil characteristics, they also contribute to ecosystem services (VOGEL et al., 2018). With regard to agricultural use of soil resources five soil functions are relevant: biomass production, storing and filtering of water, storing and recycling of nutrients, habitat for organisms and carbon

storage (HELMING et al., 2018; VOGEL et al., 2018). The categorisation of ecosystem services provided by soils always faces the challenge of fully accounting for the underlying supporting processes that contribute to regulating, provisioning and cultural services (DOMINATI et al., 2010; MEA, 2005). The more recent categorisation by The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity (TEEB) and the Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services (CICES) focus on final services to humans and therefore soil ecosystem services such as "soil formation and composition" are neglected in the most recent CICES version V5.1 (HAINES-YOUNG & POTSCHIN, 2018). The relevant ecosystem service that is subject to the identified driver, the *Bioeconomy Strategy*, can be found in the CICES-class "cultivated plants (...) grown as a source of energy" (code 1.1.1.3) which belongs to the division "biomass" under the section "provisioning services". However, the pressures and impacts resulting from the driver have manifold effects on soil ecosystem services, which are mainly listed under "regulation and maintenance services" in CICES V5.1. Changes in soil functions can be expected to also affect the "regulation of baseline flows and extreme events", providing "control of erosion rates" (code 2.2.1.1) and "buffering and attenuation of mass movement" (code 2.2.1.2) (HAINES-YOUNG & POTSCHIN, 2018).

Response

A decline in ecosystem services that are relevant for human well-being might induce a **response** at governance level (Fig.6, (5)). The establishment of new policy instruments or an adjustment of existing targets can be used to tackle environmental problems that occur as a result of the existing policies. As policies that act as drivers can have unintended implications, it can be necessary to assess the impacts repeatedly in accordance with the DPSIR framework. In the context of sustainable resource use, adjusted drivers aim for a reduction of pressures on the state of the soil system in order to avoid adverse environmental impacts on soil functions and consequently also soil ecosystem services that are relevant for human well-being. With regard to soil erosion, adjustments to soil protection policies aim for integrating soil conservation practices in soil management in order to minimise the erosion risk. According to BLANCO-CANQUI & RUIS (2018), no-till farming increases water infiltration and wet soil aggregate stability and hence, no-tillage has been identified as a measure to mitigate water erosion. Strategies to cover the soil with vegetation or harvest residues and contour farming can avoid downhill sediment transport (VALENTIN et al., 2005). Besides no-tillage or reduced tillage, cover crops and contour farming, also landscape-scale elements such as stone walls, grass margins or buffer strips have been identified as effective measures to reduce the risk of soil erosion by water (Fig.6, (B)) (PANAGOS et al., 2015a).

5 Analysis of Erosion Control Policies

5.1 Policy Instruments for Erosion Control at EU Level and in Germany

As scientific findings on the contribution of soils to ecosystem services and corresponding beneficial effects to human well-being are increasingly acknowledged at the political level, soil conservation is a relevant objective in various environmental policies recently adopted by the EU (COM(2011) 571, 2011; DEC(2013)1386, 2013; DIRECTIVE 2014/52/EU, 2014). However, due to the cross-cutting nature of soil, so far there is no binding soil-specific legislation on European level (PALEARI, 2017). After adopting the *Soil Thematic Strategy* (COM(2006)231, 2006) in 2006, a *Proposal for a Soil Framework Directive* (COM(2006)232, 2006) failed to obtain the necessary majority in the European Council and was finally withdrawn in 2014. As a result the *Soil Thematic Strategy's* main objective of ensuring sustainable soil use through the adoption of a binding *Soil Protection Directive* has not been achieved. Consequently, according to the subsidiarity principle member states are expected to set their own objectives and targets for soil conservation (PALEARI, 2017). Thus, member states have the freedom to adapt policies to environmental and farming conditions in their territories (KUTTER et al., 2011); however, this approach led to the development of a complex structure of soil legislations in all member states, with soil conservation objectives often being only indirectly addressed across several governance levels and policy domains (PALEARI, 2017).

Soil erosion by water is widely seen as a severe threat to agricultural soils in Europe (GLÄSNER et al., 2014; JONES et al., 2012). The assessment of environmental policy instruments on erosion control in Germany requires a screening of relevant documents at European, national and regional level. Due to the legal system of the EU, this comprises *strategies, regulations, directives, decisions* as well as the corresponding and supplementary documents at member state level. Only those policy documents were reviewed that explicitly mention soil erosion by water as a threat to agricultural soils. The only exception are three policy documents regarding the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) of the EU, which are reviewed as an entity regardless of their mention of erosion as a threat to soils. As a result of federalism in Germany, laws and ordinances act as a legal framework for the implementation on the regional level of the German federal states. Consequently, the practice of erosion control according to local legal requirements can only be assessed by reviewing policy documents of the German federal states ("Länder"). Due to varying complexity of erosion control legislation in the federal states, the scope of the regional analysis is limited to a study area of three federal states – Saxony, Bavaria and Baden-Wuerttemberg.

In subsection 5.1, relevant policy documents at the EU level and at the level of the Federal Republic of Germany are identified and analysed with regard to their relevance to erosion control. Furthermore, German policy documents are categorised according to their level of binding legal force for the farmers. In the second subsection (5.2) the implementation of the reviewed policy instruments at regional level is assessed. Differences in erosion control policies in Saxony, Bavaria and Baden-Wuerttemberg are identified. Furthermore, local erosion

risk assessment practices in Saxony are examined in a GIS-Analysis. Finally, the effectiveness of current erosion control measures is discussed in subsection 5.3.

5.1.1 Legislation on Erosion Control at EU level

Legal acts in EU secondary legislation are differentiated according to their level of legal force. In this hierarchy *regulations* have the most immediate effect on the member states; as soon as they enter into force they are directly applicable and have an overriding effect on all national laws on the same subject matter with no need to be transposed into national law. *Directives* are binding as well, but their objectives have to be implemented by the member states in national law within a set period of time. This transposition enables member states to take national circumstances into account and gives them more freedom in choice of form and methods to achieve the goals set by the directive. *Decisions* are only binding for those to whom they are addressed, whereas *recommendations* and *opinions* are defined as non-binding guidelines (BUX, 2018). As opinions might only have a low impact on German national legislation and recommendations mainly focus on country-specific guidance to enhance its economic performance, only regulations, directives and decisions were reviewed with regard to their relevance to erosion control. Due to their function as guidelines which set priorities for the development of more binding legislation *strategic initiatives* were reviewed as well.

In this review six EU policy documents with relevance to erosion control were identified: two strategies, one decision and three regulations concerning CAP (Tab.3).

Tab. 3: The reviewed policy documents with relevance to erosion control at European level

Title	Reference	Sections with relevance to erosion control
Roadmap to a Resource Efficient Europe	COM (2011) 571	Milestone for land and soil resources (Section 4.6)
Thematic Strategy for Soil Protection/ Proposal for a Soil Framework Directive	COM (2006) 231/ COM (2006) 232	Legal elements of the proposal (Section 3)
7 th Environmental Action Programme	DEC (2013) 1386	Thematic Priorities (Section 28)
Regulation on Direct Payments	(EU) No 1307/2013	Greening (Art. 43-47)
Regulation on Financing, Management and Monitoring of the CAP	(EU) No 1306/2013	Cross-Compliance (GAEC) (Art. 91-95, Annex II)
Regulation on Support for Rural Development by the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development	(EU) No 1305/2013	Agri-environment-climate payments (Art.28)

*highlighted regulations belong to CAP framework

The *Thematic Strategy for Soil Protection*, adopted in 2006, aims at "ensuring sustainable use of soil" while preventing soil degradation and restoring degraded soils (COM(2006)231, 2006: 5). Besides its core objective, the proposal of a Soil Framework Directive with binding targets, it aims for a better integration of soil protection in national and community policies, increasing public awareness and closing knowledge gaps by further research on soil functions and processes. The *Roadmap to a Resource Efficient Europe* is supposed to contribute to the transformation of the European economy towards more sustainable resource use, addressing various environmental assets, inter alia, land and soils (COM(2011) 571, 2011). Even though the implementation of both strategies is mandatory for the member states, the content mainly comprises guidelines for the achievement of broader objectives, acting as a framework for the development of more specific policy documents. Consequently, member states have a lot of freedom to determine how to achieve the strategic goals. As the proposal for a *Soil Framework Directive* has been withdrawn by the European Commission, environmental standards for soil management are mainly set by several regulations within the framework of the CAP. Even though these regulations are directly applicable and by definition binding for the member states, the rules outlined here apply merely to those farmers funded by the support scheme of the CAP ((EU)1307/2013, 2013). However, as member states can set additional requirements, the implications for farmers can differ at national level. The 7th *Environmental Action Plan* outlines an Environmental Programme until 2020 under the guiding principle "Living well, within the limits of our planet", which is supposed to be achieved by 2050 (DEC(2013)1386, 2013). Despite the binding character of a decision adopted by European Parliament and the Council, the 7th *Environmental Action Programme* sets out more general priority objectives while putting the member states in charge of implementation of appropriate action.

In accordance with their purpose as strategies, neither the *Thematic Strategy for Soil Protection* nor the *Roadmap to a Resource Efficient Europe* formulate any specific targets or objectives with regard to erosion control. However, both policy documents recognise soil erosion as a severe threat to soil resources and aim for its reduction. In an outline for the legislative *Proposal for a Soil Framework Directive*, the *Thematic Strategy* requests the member states to identify specific risk areas, setting targets and adopting appropriate measures to tackle soil erosion. Also the Roadmap asks member states to "implement the actions needed for reducing erosion" as part of one of its milestones concerning land and soil resources which aims at a reduction of soil erosion by 2020. Due to adverse impacts of erosion by water on 25 % of the EU's territory, the 7th *Environmental Action Programme* defines soil erosion as an urgent threat to key ecosystem services. As a result, the Programme aims in its first priority objective "to protect, conserve and enhance the Union's natural capital" (DEC(2013)1386, 2013: 178) for sustainable land management with adequate soil protection. In order to achieve this objective, efforts to reduce soil erosion should be increased by adopting targets on soil and land resources.

In the context of its three general policy objectives – viable food production, sustainable management of natural resources and climate action and a balanced territorial develop-

ment – the CAP provides payments to EU member states, funded by the European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF) and the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) ((EU)1306/2013, 2013). As soils are a crucial natural resource for all agricultural activities, the CAP includes provisions for sustainable soil management. The support scheme of the CAP is structured as two "pillars", comprising direct payments and funding for additional voluntary measures. Within the framework of the CAP the *Regulation on Direct Payments* ((EU)1307/2013, 2013) and the *Regulation on Financing, Management and Monitoring of the CAP* ((EU)1306/2013, 2013) offer a basic payment to farmers based on the size of their farmland in hectares (pillar 1). In return farmers are required to comply with a set of standards on human, animal and plant health, the environment, climate change, good agricultural condition of land and animal welfare ((EU)1306/2013, 2013: Art. 91). This set of basic rules is referred to as *Cross-Compliance* as it applies to both pillars of the funding scheme and covers two elements: *Statutory Management Requirements* (SMRs) that cover environmental legislative requirements and *Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions* (GAECs) that set standards for safeguarding soils, biodiversity and water. GAEC 5 refers directly to the objective of limiting erosion by "minimum land management reflecting site specific conditions" which is also indirectly addressed in GAEC 4 by requiring "minimum soil cover" ((EU)1306/2013, 2013: An. II). Based on these criteria, the member states are obliged to define more precise standards for "good agricultural and environmental condition of land" ((EU)1306/2013, 2013: Art. 94). In addition to the basic payment, farmers are eligible for the greening payment if they apply three measures that are beneficial for the environment and climate: crop diversification, maintenance of permanent grassland and ecological focus areas ((EU)1307/2013, 2013: Art. 43).

The prevention of soil erosion and the improvement of soil management are also covered by one of the Union's priorities for rural development, stated in the *Regulation on Support for Rural Development by the EAFRD* ((EU)1305/2013, 2013) (pillar 2). Here, voluntary measures contributing to sustainable rural development, set in the Rural Development Programmes (RDP) of member states, are co-financed by the European Agricultural Fund of Rural Development (EAFRD). Under the objective of, inter alia, "ensuring the sustainable management of natural resources and climate action" ((EU)1305/2013, 2013: 499), funding is provided to farmers whose commitments go beyond mandatory standards in order to make a positive contribution to the environment and climate. The implementation of these so-called *Agri-Environment-Climate Measures* (AECM) on the national or regional level of the member states is compulsory, but it is supposed to be adjusted to local specific needs and priorities. At least 30 % of the EAFRD financial contribution to each RDP are reserved for AECM without allowing double funding for environmental measures for instance already covered by greening payments in pillar 1.

At European level no binding targets or thresholds are set for the assessment or mitigation of soil erosion risk by water. However, sustainable land management with the aim of preserving the EU natural capital and a reduction of the erosion risk are defined objectives of all reviewed environmental policy documents. In this regard, the CAP framework

sets the most legally binding and also the most concrete requirements for erosion control by obliging the member states to minimise tillage while considering local environmental factors, stated in GAEC standard 5. Furthermore, additional financial incentives for the provision of AECM have a high potential to contribute to more sustainable land management and also erosion control, depending on their implementation on the regional level. Due to the principle of subsidiarity and in order to account for local environmental and legal conditions in the individual member states, all reviewed policies put the member states in charge of the definition of more specific measures and targets while transposing the EU strategies, decisions and regulations into national frameworks and legislation.

5.1.2 Legislation on Erosion Control in Germany

Soil protection in Germany is directly addressed by the *Federal Soil Protection Act* (BBodSchG) and the corresponding ordinance, the *Federal Soil Protection and Contaminated Sites Ordinance* (BBodSchV), with the aim to sustainably secure or restore soil functions (Tab.4). However, the focus lies on management of soil contamination, including setting standards for remediation, while applying the precautionary principle to avoid any negative impacts on soil functions. With regard to agricultural land use the BBodSchG requires compliance with principles of good agricultural practice to maintain soil fertility and its functions as a natural resource (§17 BBodSchG). This paragraph also refers to soil erosion risk management: Besides the general requirement to consider local conditions in soil management decisions, any soil loss is to be avoided by taking environmental factors such as slope, water and wind conditions and vegetation cover into account (§17 (2) 4 BBodSchG). Advisory service on the implementation of the principles of good agricultural practice is assigned to the federal states' responsibility. The corresponding ordinance (BBodSchV) specifies the assessment of harmful soil changes by water erosion (§8 BBodSchV) and refers to the federal state agricultural authorities' responsibility to take appropriate measures. On behalf of the Federal Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Forestry experts published a booklet on *Good Agricultural Practices in Soil Management and Soil Protection* (AID, 2015), giving recommendations on measures for reducing soil erosion by water.

The European Regulations have been directly converted into German legislation; Regulation (EU) No 1307/2013 is implemented by *DirektZahlDurchfG* and the corresponding ordinance, *DirektZahlDurchfV*, regulating direct and greening payments. Regulation (EU) No 1306/2013 has been transposed into *AgrarZahlVerpflG* and *AgrarZahlVerpflV* which fulfils the European member states' requirement to implement the definitions and standards of SMRs and GAEC in national legislation. The requirement of GAEC 5 of "minimum land management reflecting site specific conditions" is transposed into §6 *AgrarZahlVerpflV* (*Mindestpraktiken der Bodenbearbeitung zur Begrenzung von Erosion*) and requires the federal states to categorise arable land according to its erosion risk, calculated according to DIN19708 (2017) (*AgrarZahlVerpflV*, An. II). In the resulting categories with erosion risk by water, CC_{wasser1} and CC_{wasser2} , no tillage or only reduced tillage is allowed. Furthermore, tillage practices are restricted for fields with row crop cultivation. However, the federal state governments

Tab. 4: The reviewed policy documents with relevance to erosion control in Germany

Title	Reference	Sections with relevance to erosion control	Type
Soil Protection Act	BBodSchG, BBodSchV	Principles of good agricultural practice (BBodSchG §17; BBodSchV §8, An. IV)	mandatory
Act on Direct Payments (implementation of EU No.1307/2013)	Direktzahl-DurchfG, Direktzahl-DurchfV	Crop diversification, permanent grassland, ecological focus areas (DirektzahlDurchfG §18; DirektzahlDurchfV §17-19b, 28, 30-31)	mandatory
Act on Requirements and Standards for Agricultural Payments (implementation of EU No.1306/2013)	AgrarZahl-VerpflG, Agrar-ZahlVerpflV	GAEC standard (AgrarZahlVerpflG §2; AgrarZahlVerpflV §5-6, An. II)	mandatory
Framework Plan for the Joint Task "Improvement of Agricultural Structures and Coastal Protection", 2017-2020	GAKG	Catch crops/winter greening, reduction of erosion risk (Framework Plan, section 4.C)	incentive-based
National Framework for Rural Development (NRR)		AECM (10.1) (NRR, section 5.2.6.3.2)	incentive-based

are entitled to specify diverging requirements. The minimum soil cover requirements as introduced by GAEC 4 are implemented in § 5 AgrarZahlVerpflV.

As stated in (EU) Regulation No 1305/2013, the AECM have to be included into national rural development programmes. Due to federalism most of the German federal states develop their own Rural Development Programmes (RDP), which results in 13 different RDP in Germany. All RDP address several AECM and are hence co-financed by the EAFRD and the federal states for the current programming period of 2014 – 2020 (BMEL, 2018a). In addition to EU-funding, the Länder can receive financial support from the federal state (Bund). Such a joint task is only possible due to the national importance of an "improvement of the agrarian structure and of coastal preservation" (German Basic Law, article 91a). Thus the "Joint Task for the Improvement of Agricultural Structures and Coastal Protection" (GAK) was adopted and defined in the *GAK Act* (GAKG). The allocation of funding within the scope of the GAK is finalised for a four-year planning period (currently: *Rahmenplan der Gemeinschaftsaufgabe "Verbesserung der Agrarstruktur und des Küstenschutzes" für den Zeitraum 2017-2020*). In order to facilitate the authorisation by the EAFRD, those AECM and other measures that are implemented in several federal states and co-financed by the GAK-funding scheme are summarised in the National Framework for Rural Development (NRR). For instance, catch crop cultivation combined with a renouncement of chemical plant protection agents and mineral fertilisers belong to one AECM with relevance to erosion control defined in the NRR – which requires the federal states to determine the duration of intercropping within the

cultivation season.

Due to their nature as federal acts compliance with BBodSchG, DirektzahlDurchfG and AgrarZahlVerpflG as well as with the corresponding ordinances is mandatory for farmers (Tab.4). However, only the BBodSchG addresses all landowners and requires compliance with principles of good agricultural practice for any use of agricultural soils, whereas DirektzahlDurchfG and AgrarZahlVerpflG merely apply to farmers who receive direct payments. Due to most farmers' dependence on direct payments, both pieces of legislation are categorised as mandatory. Furthermore, the degree of legal obligation of the reviewed policy documents is a continuum from voluntary incentive-based measures to mandatory provisions. Thus, legislation referring to agri-environment-climate measures is classified as incentive-based as these measures are voluntary and decoupled from cross-compliance requirements.

The EU provisions on cross-compliance, greening and AECM were transposed into German law and supplement existing soil protection policies such as the BBodSchG. The requirements of GAEC 5 are implemented by AgrarZahlVerpflV and restrict farmers' soil management decisions significantly on sites categorised as prone to water erosion. The AECM and additional environmental measures funded by the federal state as well as the EAFRD and German federal states offer financial support to offset financial loss resulting e.g. from catch crop cultivation for erosion control. Compliance with principles of good agricultural practice is mandatory for every owner of agricultural land in Germany. However, neither the legal text nor the corresponding booklet on practical advice published by the BMEL entail any binding thresholds or targets for a reduction of soil loss by water, which makes monitoring its implementation difficult.

5.2 Implementation at regional level

5.2.1 Legislation on Erosion Control in Bavaria, Saxony and Baden-Wuerttemberg

Due to federalism German federal state governments are supposed to implement national laws into federal state legislation. With regard to erosion control policies, measures defined in federal laws on cross-compliance and AECM are transposed into regional legislation. In accordance with AgrarZahlVerpflV §6 and the cross-compliance legislation, the three federal states reviewed in this study – Saxony, Bavaria and Baden-Wuerttemberg – adopted their own regulations on erosion control:

- **SächsGAPAnfVO** – Saxony
- **EschV** – Bavaria
- **ErosionsSchV** – Baden-Wuerttemberg

As determined by AgrarZahlverpflV the erosion risk of agricultural fields is categorised based on DIN19708 (2017). The federal states made use of their right to choose the number

of additional factors to be considered in the calculation besides the soil's erodibility (K-factor) and the slope (S-factor). Bavaria and Baden-Wuerttemberg use only these two factors for the calculation of the local erosion risk, whereas Saxony also takes the rainfall erosivity (R-factor) into account. On field units categorised as CC_{wasser1} (erosion risk) tillage is banned between 1st December and 15th February unless erosion control measures such as slope-parallel tillage are applied. In addition to the restriction during the winter, fields categorised as CC_{wasser2} (high erosion risk) must only be ploughed just immediately before sowing, while any tillage is prohibited before sowing row cultures with row spacing greater 45 cm (AgrarZahlVerpflV §6).

According to AgrarZahlVerpflV the federal states can determine diverging requirements for soil management to account for local climatic conditions, preferences of specific crops or difficulties for appropriate monitoring. While Saxony allows ploughing on CC_{wasser1} -fields if no other soil cultivation takes place before 15th February (SächsGAPAnfVO §2), Bavaria suspends the regulations on reduced tillage for the cultivation of early summer crops and if farmers implement slope-parallel grass strips for erosion control (EschV §4). With reference to challenges of monitoring small fields, in Baden-Wuerttemberg common field units ("Flurstücke") are merged to larger fields ("Schlag") (Fig.7). The erosion risk is firstly assessed for the smaller units and hence, the larger field's risk class is derived from the erosion risk values of the merged fields. The erosion risk class covering more than 50 % of the area is decisive for the new field unit's erosion risk class. However, if both classes cover the same area size, the lower erosion risk class is assigned to the new field, whereas three different adjacent erosion risk classes (CC_{wasser1} , CC_{wasser2} and CC_{wasser0}) with less than 50 % each lead to a categorisation as CC_{wasser1} (ErosionsSchV §6). As the farmers can decide which adjacent fields are merged to one, this approach facilitates a downgrading of the erosion risk classes without applying any erosion control measures to the fields.

Fig. 7: Example for merging fields with different erosion risk classes into one *Schlag* in Baden-Wuerttemberg, from a leaflet published by the Ministry of Rural Development and Consumer Protection (MLR) in Baden-Wuerttemberg (MLR, 2017)

Besides erosion control in the context of cross-compliance, AECM are implemented in the Rural Development Programmes (RDP) of German federal states. The reduction of soil loss by water erosion is subject of AECMs in all reviewed federal states. However, both the number and type of erosion control measures and the corresponding financial support provided to the farmers vary (Tab.5). In general four erosion control measures receive financial support: grass strips on the fields, reduced or no-till farming methods, catch crops/intercropping and winter greening. Due to the independent legislation on federal state level farmers in Saxony can receive €80/ha for no-till farming, whereas in Bavaria such measures are only funded for row crop cultivation and in Baden-Wuerttemberg reduced tillage with strip-till method is

remunerated with €120/ha.

Tab. 5: Overview of AECM with relevance to erosion control in three exemplary federal states, based on the respective policy documents: Funding Guideline Agri-Environment-Climate Measures (AUK/2015), Cultural Landscape Programme (KULAP) and Administrative Regulation on the Support programme for Agri-Environment, Climate Protection and Animal Welfare (VwV FAKT)

Federal state	Policy document	Measures with relevance to erosion control	Annual financial support
Saxony	AUK/2015	AL1: grass strips on agricultural fields	€313/ha
		AL2: no-till farming/direct sowing	€80/ha
		AL4: catch crop cultivation	€78/ha
		AL7: wintering stubble	€100/ha
Bavaria	KULAP	B34: riparian strips for erosion control; grass strips on ecological focus areas	€920/ha; €380/250/ha
		B36: winter greening with intercropping/wild plant species	€40-70/ha; €90-120/ha
		B37/38: mulch/strip or direct sowing methods for row crop cultivation	€70-150/ha
Baden-Wuerttemberg	VwV FAKT	F1: winter greening	€100/ha
		F4: reduced tillage with strip-till method	€120/ha

Measures for erosion control at federal state level are mainly based on cross-compliance provisions and on voluntary AECM. As a result of the application of the subsidiarity principle, the German federal states have some degree of freedom in the implementation of national laws. Even though the erosion risk assessment is precisely stipulated by a DIN-standard, the respective regulations in Saxony, Bavaria and Baden-Wuerttemberg vary with regard to calculation methods and resulting restrictions to farmers' soil management decisions. Also the implementation of AECM in regional RDP led to different funding schemes for the provision of varying environmental measures.

5.2.2 Consideration of Local Environmental Conditions for Erosion Risk Assessment in Saxony

Taking local environmental factors into account is the precondition to the adoption of any sustainable soil management scheme for a reduction of soil erosion. Among many measures for erosion control that have been identified during the review of relevant policy documents, the most concrete provision is the requirement for German federal states to assess and categorise the natural soil erosion risk. In chapter 5.2.1 the degree of freedom for the implementation of AgrarZahlVerpflV in the individual German federal states has been discussed. Due to the importance of soil erosion risk classes for imposing restrictions on farmers' soil management decisions, in this subsection the classification process is examined in a GIS analysis.

Due to difficulties with the acquisition of geodata from the respective federal states, the analysis is limited to Saxony. The erosion risk classes are supposed to represent the natural erosion risk, i.e. the erosion risk resulting from environmental and not anthropogenic factors. As a result each federal state's Erosionskataster is based on soil erodibility, slope steepness and optionally rainfall erosivity. In the absence of extensive in-situ measurements of soil loss, the regularly updated Erosionsatlas is taken as an approximation of the real natural erosion risk and displays the expected average annual soil loss in tons per hectare. Due to political decisions, both map layers are based on the same three factors, but on different input data (Tab.6).

Tab. 6: Input data used for the compilation of the Erosionskataster and the Erosionsatlas in Saxony

Erosion Factor	Cross-Compliance Erosionskataster	Erosionsatlas
Soil Erodibility (K-factor)	soil map with resolution 1 :200 000 (Source: LfULG)	soil map with resolution 1 :50 000 (Source: LfULG)
Slope Steepness (S-factor)	DEM with a resolution of 20 m (Source: GeoSn)	DEM with a resolution of 5 m (Source: GeoSn)
Rain Erosivity (R-factor)	rainfall series from 1952-2004 (Source: DEW)	rainfall series from 1993-2012 (Source: DEW)

As a result the proportion of areas with high erosion risk values differ in the Erosionskataster and the Erosionsatlas. According to the erosionskataster 58.25 % out of 943 184 ha of agricultural land in Saxony have no erosion risk, whereas the Erosionsatlas classifies only 43.18 % as "no erosion risk by water". On the other hand the Erosionsatlas ascribes "high" and "very high" risk values to approx. 37 % and 20 % of land area respectively, while only approx. 27 % and 15 % have such a high erosion risk according to the Erosionskataster (Tab.7).

Tab. 7: Proportions of areas with erosion risk values according to Erosionskataster and Erosionsatlas

Classified Erosion Risk	Area in ha in Erosionskataster	Area in ha in Erosionsatlas
0	549 401 (58.25%)	407 247 (43.18%)
1	251 696 (26.69%)	346 845 (36.77%)
2	142 088 (15.06%)	189 092 (20.05%)
	943 184 ha	943 184 ha

The spatial distribution of these diverging risk values is displayed in the difference map in Fig.8. A map with a higher resolution can be found in the annex. Both the difference map as well as Tab.8 illustrate the differences between the erosion risk classification in the Erosionskataster and the Erosionsatlas. Areas classified as 0 indicate an identical risk classification in both maps, whereas values 1 and 2 indicate that the erosion risk is one or two classes lower in the Erosionskataster compared to the Erosionsatlas. As it is assumed that the Erosionsatlas reflects the natural conditions more realistically, here the erosion risk is underestimated. Negative values are ascribed to those areas where the erosion risk is actually higher in the Erosionskataster than in the Erosionsatlas.

Fig. 8: Map of differences of erosion risk values according to Erosionskataster and Erosionsatlas. 1 and 2 indicate differences by one or two risk classes, respectively.

The comparison of both erosion risk assessments has shown that almost 24 % of the total area of Saxony has a lower erosion risk class in the Erosionskataster than in the Erosionsatlas. As the Erosionsatlas' accuracy is expected to be higher due to higher data resolution and updated rainfall series, this discrepancy can be seen as the quota of misclassification. Despite approx. 71 % of consistent classifications, this deviation has significant implications for the total area of fields with restrictions in soil management for erosion control.

Tab. 8: Calculated differences between Erosionsatlas (A) and Erosionskataster (B) in Saxony

Level of Difference	Area in ha	% of total area
0: same category	673133.00	71.37
1: one category higher in A	210470.00	22.31
2: two categories higher in A	13573.90	1.4
-1: one category higher in B	43480.70	4.6
-2: two categories higher in B	2490.07	0.26
	943 147.67	100

5.3 Effectiveness of Current Erosion Control Policies

The effectiveness of policy instruments for erosion control is evaluated based on targets and degree of legal force, the implementation practice at regional level and the implemented control and enforcement schemes.

Targets and Degree of Legal Force

The review of policy documents with regard to concrete erosion control measures has shown that only few policy instruments directly address soil erosion by water and even fewer set legally binding requirements or targets for erosion control. The only policy documents going beyond the vague identification of erosion by water as a threat to soil resources are the regulations within the CAP Framework at European level as well as the corresponding legislation at national and regional level (Tab.9). The sections on greening ((EU)1307/2013, 2013: Art. 43-47), Cross-compliance ((EU)1306/2013, 2013: Art. 91-95, An. II) and agri-environment-climate payments ((EU)1305/2013, 2013: Art. 28) comprise concrete measures for erosion control. Although European regulations are directly applicable and legally binding legislation in all member states as soon as they enter into force, the CAP Framework primarily applies to those farmers who apply for funding support. As the CAP is based on incentive-based instruments, compliance with environmental standards such as GAEC is financially encouraged, but not mandatory to every user. However, in 2016 316 000 applicants from agricultural holdings in Germany received direct payments in the total amount of €4.8 billion (BMEL, 2017), whereas the agricultural structure survey recorded only 275 400 farms in 2016 (DESTATIS, 2016). As agricultural statistics only include farms which reach one of various thresholds in terms of size, such as 5 ha of farmland or certain numbers of livestock, they are outnumbered by the large number of applications for direct payments¹.

These figures suggest that most farms in Germany depend on the contribution of subsidies from direct payments to their total income and therefore, compliance with cross-compliance and greening are considered as a mandatory legal requirement. In addition to applications for funding through direct payments, 189 944 contracts on a total amount of €511 million for AECM were concluded in 2016 (BMEL, 2018b). The lower volume of financial support as well as the comparatively small number of contracts concluded on AECM, indicate that this policy instrument offers a financial incentive, while it is nevertheless the farmer's voluntary decision to conclude contracts on additional environmental measures.

The most specific standards for erosion control are set by the regulation on cross-compliance, whereas greening measures have a rather indirect impact and the relevance of AECM to erosion control depends on their implementation by the German federal states. The standards for GAEC as defined in the cross-compliance regulation require a limitation of soil erosion by minimising land management and the provision of minimum soil cover. Consequently, German national legislation restricts soil tillage in areas with high erosion risks. However, due to federalism, German federal states are entitled to implement derogations to the risk assessment process and also to the resulting restrictions to soil cultivation. Greening mea-

¹Dr. Hubertus Wolfgarten, Referat 617 für Direktzahlungen, BMEL, written correspondence on 4 October 2018

Tab. 9: Summary of reviewed policy documents which include concrete measures for erosion control at European, national and regional level

EU legislation	National legislation	Regional legislation
Regulation on Direct Payments (EU) No 1307/2013 Greening (Art. 43-47)	Direktzahl-DurchfG, DirektzahlDurchfV Crop diversification, permanent grassland, ecological focus areas (DirektzahlDurchfG §18; DirektzahlDurchfV §17-19b, 28, 30-31)	
Regulation on Financing, Management and Monitoring of the CAP (EC) No 1306/2013 Cross-Compliance (GAEC standards) (Art. 91-95, An. II)	AgrarZahlVerpflG, AgrarZahlVerpflV GAEC standard (AgrarZahlVerpflG §2; AgrarZahlVerpflV §5-6, An. II)	Saxony: SächsGAPAnfVO; Bavaria: EschV; Baden-Wurtemberg: ErosionsSchV
Regulation on Support for Rural Development by the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) (EU) No 1305/2013 Agri-environment-climate payments (Art. 28)	Rahmenplan der Gemeinschaftsaufgabe "Verbesserung der Agrarstruktur und des Küstenschutzes", 2017-2020 (GAKG) Catch crops/winter greening, reduction of erosion risk (Framework Plan, section 4.C) and National Framework for Rural Development (NRR) AECM (NRR, section 5.2.6.3.2)	Saxony: Funding Guideline Agri-Environment-Climate Measures (AUK/2015); Bavaria: Cultural Landscape (KULAP); Baden-Wuerttemberg: Administrative Regulation on the Support Programme for Agri-Environment, climate protection and animal welfare (VwV FAKT)

*highlighted sections indicate relevance for erosion control

asures affect the erosion risk rather indirectly via diversification of crops, the conservation of permanent grassland and provision of ecological focus areas can reduce the erosion risk in contrast to large fields of monoculture plantations. The impact of erosion control measures implemented as AECM might vary as number, type and financial support per measure differ in each federal state. Even though compliance with AECM measures is voluntary, they have the potential to reduce the erosion risk by setting specific requirements, such as no-till farming or winter greening, and offer to reimburse farmers for resulting financial losses.

Implementation Practices at Regional Level

As soil erosion by water is a local phenomenon, the consideration of local environmental conditions and regional political decisions on erosion risk management are highly decisive for the effectiveness of erosion control measures. In the process of transposing federal laws

into regional legislation, German federal states have the right to specify rules of application and can also make minor adjustments or add requirements. With regard to erosion control, the GAEC standards as well as the AECM are implemented by more specific, regional regulations, whereas greening measures along with direct payments are regulated by federal law (Tab.3). The implementation of AECM as a policy instrument based on financial incentives varies among the different RDP of each federal state. Consequently, the number and type of measures dedicated to erosion control as well as the related financial support illustrate the importance, assigned to erosion as a threat to soils and the environment in the respective federal state. However, the independent choice of environmental measures and funding schemes enables the federal states to account for local soil management and farming conditions. As there is no legal obligation for farmers to apply AECM, a comprehensive list of incentive-based measures for erosion control in a specific federal state is not necessarily an indicator for advances in soil protection. For the consideration of the local erosion risk by water as defined in the GAEC standards, the federal states can adjust both the assessment methods stipulated by the DIN standard as well as the corresponding restrictions to soil management in areas with high erosion risks. It can be assumed that local authorities have to balance between safeguarding soils by specifying strict erosion control measures and the economic situation at farm level. The review of the respective regulations in Saxony, Bavaria and Baden-Wuerttemberg, as well as the GIS-analysis of spatial data used to display and assess the erosion risk in Saxony, demonstrated that this conflict of interests can undermine the political intention of contributing to soil conservation.

Although the categorisation for erosion risk classes stated in AgrarZahlVerpflV refers to DIN19708 (2017), the erosion risk of five DIN classes "very low" to "high" is neglected and classified as "no erosion risk". The simplified classification is implemented in regional legislation of all federal states reviewed in this study. However, this approach contradicts the precautionary principle of German Good Agricultural Practice and the BBodSchG which aim for avoiding any harmful impact on soil resources. Furthermore, the minimum requirement for the assessment of the erosion risk is the consideration of the soil erodibility (K-factor) and the slope (S-factor). However, as soil erosion by water is triggered by precipitation, the rainfall erosivity factor (R-factor) is a crucial component, which is also used for the assessment of the natural erosion risk specified by DIN19708, 2017. Only Saxony chose to include the r-factor in the risk calculation, whereas Bavaria and Baden-Wuerttemberg merely use the two factors required by EU regulation. As the R-factor and the slope length (L-factor) are normally calculated for the compilation of the federal state's Erosionsatlas, it is a political decision to exclude these factors from the erosion risk assessment in the Erosionskataster. Even though the use of the L- and R-factor is optional, it can be assumed that their consideration would increase the accuracy of the resulting erosion risk maps. Besides the divergent calculation methods, the quality of the input data is decisive as has been shown by the GIS-analysis of spatial data used in Saxony. Discrepancies between the Erosionsatlas and the Erosionskataster with regard to the assessed erosion risk illustrate how the choice of input data have practical and also political impacts. The fact that approx. 24 % of the total area of Saxony would have been categorised in a higher erosion risk class according to the Erosionsatlas suggests

that there is no political interest in increasing erosion risk classes by using data with higher accuracy. The disadvantages for soil conservation cannot be explained by limitations of work capacities as more recent data with higher resolutions exists and is used for the compilation of the Erosionsatlas.

Besides adjustments of the calculation methods, the federal states offer exemptions from existing regulations, helping farmers to avoid extensive actions for erosion control. As regulations mainly apply to agricultural soils, they naturally conflict with short-term economic interests of farmers. Making political decisions concerning the regional approach to erosion risk assessment and soil protection at a regional level by the same local authorities who support and advise farmers in economic management decisions might also lead to a conflict of interests. This conflict becomes obvious when the Ministry of Rural Development and Consumer Protection (MLR) in Baden-Wuerttemberg publishes brochures to advise farmers how to reduce the classified erosion risk by the process of merging field units (MLR, 2017; Fig.7). In this case the ministry in charge of the implementation of and advisory on direct payments encourages farmers to evade environmental regulations. Also in Saxony and Bavaria, restrictions on ploughing CC_{wasser1} fields can often be evaded by applying minor measures for erosion control. As these additional regulations undermine the original intention to safeguard soils prone to erosion, the legal binding force of current legislation is negligible.

Control and Enforcement Schemes

As the policy instruments belonging to the CAP framework are drawn up as EU regulations, they are immediately applicable. The corresponding control and enforcement schemes for monitoring the implementation as well as assessing the success are specified in the EU policy documents. According to (EU)1306/2013 (2013), the implementation of rules set at EU level as well as the establishment of efficient management and control systems is in the Member States's responsibility. This so-called *integrated system* comprises an electronic database, an identification system for agricultural parcels and payment entitlements, aid applications and payment claims, an integrated control system and an identification system to record each beneficiary. For controlling requirements set in the scope of cross-compliance, member states can either use the integrated system or make use of their existing control systems, supplemented by on-the-spot checks in at least 1 % of the beneficiaries' holdings. If the beneficiary does not comply with the cross-compliance rules, the member states can impose administrative penalties, consisting of a reduction of or exclusion from payments in the course of the respective calendar year. Specifications for penalties vary from a limited reduction of 5 % – in the case of non compliance due to negligence – to a minimum reduction of 20 % in cases of intentional non-compliance (SMUL, 2018).

The Commission monitors the performance of the CAP and the compliance with cross-compliance based on reporting by the Member States. The impact of the CAP instruments is measured in relation to the CAP objectives which, inter alia, refer to environmental aspects: "sustainable management of natural resources and climate action, with a focus on greenhouse gas emissions, biodiversity, soil and water" ((EU)1306/2013, 2013: Art. 110(2)). If member

states violate the Union's rules, e.g. by exceeding the set financial ceilings, failing to comply with their duty of information or let others than the accredited paying agencies execute payments, monthly or interim payments can be suspended or reduced by the Commission for a period of up to 12 months if the deficiencies are not remedied. Furthermore, the Commission may organise on-the-spot inspections to verify the compliance of administrative practices with the Union's rules. Besides the reduction or temporary suspension of payments the Commission might also impose sanctions.

The monitoring of the implementation of specific cross-compliance obligations such as the implementation of GAEC standards takes place on the regional level and is performed by the federal state's competent authority (SMUL, 2018). As there is no legal obligation to publish the reports of on-the-spot checks, it is difficult to assess the effectiveness of this control scheme. However, according to a minor inquiry by the Green Party ("Die Grünen") the proportion of holdings in Bavaria with violations of cross-compliance amounted to 61.5 % of all inspected holdings, out of which only 2.26 % were identified as intentional non-compliance (BAYERISCHER LANDTAG, 2017). Although the number of on-the-spot-checks amounts to merely 1 % of the holdings, a proportion of 60 % of ascertained breaches suggests that many violations of cross-compliance regulations remain undiscovered due to limited capacities for direct controls.

6 Environmental Pressures from Energy Crops and Mitigation Strategies

After analysing erosion control policies and assessing their effectiveness in terms of setting binding requirements for the prevention of soil loss by water erosion, the characteristics of energy crops are examined with regard to their impact on the erosion risk. In this respect, three ecological aspects influence the sustainability of energy crop cultivation: cultivation method, harvest frequency and seasonality of vegetation cover. These aspects are related to the common cultivation practices for the respective crop as well as to the plant-specific characteristics. However, farming practices for a specific crop can also vary as they are adapted to seasonal and regional conditions and hence, in comparative studies the energy crop's impact on the erosion risk is derived from a generalised assessment of environmental pressures out of which "erosion" is just one aspect (EEA, 2006). Several studies have also tested alternative and adjusted cultivation systems on their potential for a reduction of the local erosion risk (NITZSCHE et al., 2001; GRASS et al., 2013; FNR, 2010). In terms of soil management, decisions on soil cover and soil tillage are the most important factors. Both are considered in the RUSLE as well as in the ABAG in the cover-management factor (C-factor) and the support practices factor (P-factor) (DIN19708, 2017; PANAGOS et al., 2015e). However, it is difficult to assess their mitigating effect on the local erosion risk as these factors interact with regional environmental factors, such as seasonality of rainfall.

In the following, firstly existing studies on the comparison of different energy crops with regard to their environmental pressures are reviewed and plant-specific impacts on the erosion risk are summarised in subsection 6.1. Secondly, in subsection 6.2 pressures of agricultural soil management are analysed with regard to their impacts on soil loss by water erosion in interaction with environmental factors. Furthermore, in response to increasing soil erosion risks, mitigation strategies for the prevention of soil erosion in energy crop cultivation are reviewed (6.3).

6.1 Impacts of Energy Crop Cultivation on the Erosion Risk

Several studies have assessed the environmental pressures of energy crops under Western European growing conditions (SCHULTZE et al., 2008; PETERS et al., 2010; SCHLEGEL et al., 2005; EEA, 2006; GREIFF et al., 2010). As stated above, the environmental impacts of specific crops can vary in different cultivation systems and hence, in comparative studies usually a number of selected crops is examined, assuming that they are grown under conventional farming conditions. Normally, the erosion risk associated with certain crops is just one indicator for environmental pressures on the natural asset "soil" besides other factors such as compaction, eutrophication or humus balance. The reviewed studies assign a specific erosion risk to energy crops, mostly considering crop-specific characteristics, such as row spacing, harvest frequency in an annual or perennial system and seasonal variations in vegetation cover, in particular the period of soil remaining bare without any canopy cover. In their report on renewable resources and soil protection for the German Environment Agency's (UBA)

Committee for Soil Protection, the Ecologic Institute categorised the erosion risk and other soil threats of a number of selected energy crops based on a literature review (SCHLEGEL et al., 2005). Also the EEA compiled a comprehensive report on environmental pressures of 21 categories of energy crops in order to assess sustainable bioenergy potentials in Europe (EEA, 2006). Other studies on the impairment of German nature and landscape caused by energy crop cultivation by SCHULTZE et al. (2008) and PETERS et al. (2010) use erosion risk classifications of energy crops, but are not considered in this analysis as they use the same erosion risk factors as EEA, 2006. Based on several independent assessments, GREIFF et al. (2010) classified energy crops according to the intensity of their impact on soil, water and biodiversity, while taking soil loss by erosion as an indicator for soil threats. The classified erosion risks as specified by the three aforementioned reports are summarised in Tab. 11. The first part of the table comprises the most common energy crops, including short-rotation forestry (SRF) and permanent grassland, whereas the second part lists potential energy crops with promising properties for bioenergy generation. As the latter have not been subject to many research studies yet, assessments of their erosion risk are missing in some of the reports summarised here. Furthermore, Tab.11 comprises the crop-specific C-factor, which is used by PANAGOS et al. (2015c) as a baseline for the calculation of the cover-management-factor. As a value between 0 and 1 it expresses the mitigating impact of vegetation cover on soil loss by erosion compared to bare fallow land without any vegetation (C-factor = 1). However, this C-factor differs from the C-factor according to DIN19708 (2017), which entails additional calculation steps, such as the incorporation of regional rainfall erosivity. Due to different approaches in the respective research reports, the crop-specific erosion risks summarised in Tab.11 are categorised in three, four or five classes. In order to facilitate a direct comparison of the risk values, the divergent scales were coloured according to the level of their risk intensity (Tab.10).

Tab. 10: Tabular comparison and colour assignment to divergent erosion risk classes used in Tab.11

Research Report	Soil Loss by Water Erosion				
	low risk		←→		high risk
GREIFF <i>et al.</i> , 2010	1	2	3	4	5
SCHLEGEL <i>et al.</i> , 2005	1	2	2-3	3	4
EEA, 2006	A	A/B	B	B/C	C

Among the examined energy crops, starch and sugar plants, such as **maize, potato, sugar beet, sweet sorghum** and **sudangrass** all establish a very late vegetation cover and hence, a cultivation of these crops in monoculture exacerbates the natural erosion risk. This is also represented in the respective C-factors: comparatively high C-factors indicate low soil coverage by vegetation and therefore only low mitigating effects to the erosion risk compared to bare soil without any vegetation. Furthermore, planting crops in rows with distances of 45 cm (beet root) and 75 cm (maize) and additional hilling for potato cultivation also increases the erosion risk (KALTSCHMITT et al., 2009). Consequently, all three reviewed reports assign the highest erosion risk class to maize, sugar beet and potato and even though just covered by GREIFF et al. (2010), sudangrass and sweet sorghum are also classified as

Tab. 11: Summary table of crop-specific erosion risks and corresponding C-factors derived from various research reports. In the lower part more recently and therefore scarcely researched energy crops are listed. Blank fields indicate that these crops have not been considered in the respective study.

Energy Crop		Classified Erosion Risk			C-Factor
english	latin	SCHLEGEL <i>et al.</i> , 2005	GREIFF <i>et al.</i> , 2010	EEA, 2006	PANAGOS <i>et al.</i> , 2015c
Maize	<i>zea mays</i>	4	5	C	0.38
Sugar beet	<i>beta vulgaris</i>	4	5	C	0.34
Potato	<i>solanum tuberosum</i>	4	5	C	0.34
Sunflower	<i>helianthus annuus</i>	3	4	B/C	0.32
Rapeseed	<i>brassica napus</i>	2-3	2	B	0.30
Winter cereals		2	2	A	0.20
Short-rotation forestry (SRF)		1	1	A	-
Permanent grassland		1	1	A	-
Miscanthus	<i>miscanthus x giganteus</i>	2	1	-	-
Sudangrass	<i>sorghum x dummondii</i>	-	5	-	-
Sweet sorghum	<i>sorghum bicolor</i>	-	5	-	-
Silphium perfoliatum	<i>silphium perfoliatum</i>	-	1	-	-
Switchgrass	<i>panicum virgatum</i>	-	-	A	-
Giant reed	<i>arundo donax</i>	-	-	A	-

high-risk (Tab.11). The reviewed oil plants, **sunflower** and **rapeseed**, might increase the erosion risk by providing no year-round vegetation coverage and row distances of 40-60 cm for sunflowers (KALTSCHMITT et al., 2009). However, in comparison to other energy crops they have a medium risk for soil erosion by water (Tab.11). Due to their long vegetation period **winter cereals**, such as winter wheat, triticale and rye, have a mitigating impact on soil erosion risks (KALTSCHMITT et al., 2009; EEA, 2006). This is also confirmed by the erosion risk classification and the low C-factor of cereals in general as compiled by PANAGOS et al. (2015c). **Short-rotation forestry** (SRF) and **permanent grassland** have a thoroughly positive impact on the erosion risk as a result of their year-round vegetation cover. Grown in a perennial system, SRF with poplar or willow trees require no soil management after the second year and stabilise the soil with deep rooting, which contributes to erosion control. Only during the first two years environmental pressures can exceed the benefits due to herbicide application and bare soil between the tree rows with varying distances of 0.75 to 3 m, depending on the harvest machinery used (KALTSCHMITT et al., 2009). Other lignocellulose plants, such as **miscanthus**, **switchgrass**, **giant reed** as well as **silphium perfoliatum**, sweet sorghum and sudangrass are more recently studied for the utilisation as energy crops and as a result only few impact assessments consider their environmental effects. However, their properties with regard to corresponding erosion risks are promising as they are all assigned

with a low erosion risk in the reviewed studies – except for sudangrass and sweet sorghum (Tab.11). *Miscanthus* as well as switchgrass and *silphium perfoliatum* are known to reduce soil erosion as they can be grown in perennial systems and hence, they have similar positive effects as SRF. Moreover, they provide year-round canopy cover (KALTSCHMITT et al., 2009; SCHLEGEL et al., 2005).

6.2 Anthropogenic and Environmental Impacts on Soil Erosion

Besides topographical factors, such as slope steepness and length, climatic factors of rainfall intensity and the erodibility of the soil type, soil management has a great influence on soils' susceptibility for erosion by water. In fact, tillage erosion is often considered a separate form of soil erosion in literature – besides wind and water erosion (DEUMLICH et al., 2006; SCHEFFER et al., 2018). Soil management comprises two main influencing factors: firstly, the choice of tillage practices, i.e. loosening the ground by physically disrupting the soil, whereas furrows can facilitate downhill run-off, and secondly, decisions influencing soil coverage, which is a result of the choice of cultivated crops, their specific, seasonal vegetation cover and decisions on cultivation periods, as well as additional soil coverage by mulching or leaving residues on the fields.

These factors interact and depend on the choice of crops as well as on local, environmental conditions. For instance, strong seasonality of vegetation coverage can have more or less significant impacts on the actual soil loss by erosion, depending on the seasonality of precipitation as well as slope characteristics. Soil cultivation – regardless of its direction, vertical or horizontal to the slope – always leads to downhill transport of sediments, increasing with the frequency and intensity of tillage (SCHEFFER et al., 2018). Furthermore, intensive tillage affects the erodibility of the in-situ soil as it reduces organic matter by destruction of microaggregates, leading to a decomposition of exposed organic matter. As organic matter also acts as a binding agent for microaggregates, this process results in an overall reduction of soil resistance to erosive forces (BRYAN, 2000).

Several research studies and field experiments address the factors influencing soil resistance to erosion (FATTET et al., 2011; ZUAZO & PLEGUEZUELO, 2008; GYSSELS et al., 2005; MA et al., 2014). As soils disturbed by tillage often have a non-coherent fabric, aggregation and aggregate stability become decisive factors in erosion resistance (BRYAN, 2000). In their field study on the impacts of different vegetation types on aggregate stability and shear strength, FATTET et al. (2011) found that aggregate stability was mainly correlated to the presence of very fine roots (< 0.5 mm in diameter) and the soil organic carbon content. Shear strength was found to be related to soil aggregate stability and the authors concluded that it is possible to improve aggregate stability and reduce the risk of mass movement of shallow substrates at the same time. Also GYSSELS et al. (2005) examined the effects of roots on erosion resistance and emphasised the combined effect of canopy cover and roots, whereas their impact varies according to the respective erosion form. Shallow but dense root systems seem to be most effective in resisting interrill and rill erosion, whereas neither root density

nor root length density have any influence on soil loss by splash erosion (GYSSELS et al., 2005). For a reduction of rain splash detachment vegetation parameters, especially the canopy cover, have been identified as the crucial factors (MA et al., 2014). In field experiments MA et al. (2014) measured a reduction of the average splash detachment rate under crop canopies of 68 % compared to bare soil. However, they also found splash erosion greater than on bare land between some corn rows, which occasionally led to a concentration of splash erosion in central rows. In their review on soil erosion and run-off prevention by plant covers, ZUAZO & PLEGUEZUELO (2008) conclude that the exponential connection between the decline of erosion by water with both vegetation cover and root mass has to feed into erosion management strategies.

6.3 Mitigation Strategies in Soil Management

Although it is difficult to predict the regional thresholds of various impact factors beyond which soil erosion by water occurs, several rules of thumb facilitate a rough assessment of critical local conditions: loamy sand and sandy loam, especially in slope areas with a gradient > 4 % are prone to water erosion (SCHLEGEL et al., 2005). Heavy precipitation has more devastating effects than constant rain with less intensity (BRYAN, 2000). Furthermore, soil coverage < 50 % further increases the erosion susceptibility of arable soils, especially of loose soil after tillage (DEUMLICH et al., 2006). As the review of recent research results has shown (6.2), soil resistance to erosive forces can be supported by preserving soil aggregates, supporting the establishment of a dense and fine root system and providing a dense canopy cover. Consequently, erosion control measures mainly consist of reducing the intensity of soil cultivation in order to reduce adverse impacts on soil stability by adjusting tillage practices and of increasing soil cover in terms of soil-surface cover and vegetation canopy. As the development of extensive systems of fine roots need more time, annual cultivation systems often use residues or catch crops to provide soil cover and prevent soil loss by run-off.

In a long-term field experiment (since 1992) NITZSCHE et al. (2001) observed effects of four different tillage treatments on soil erosion and soil properties. In their evaluation of the trials, conservation tillage with a cultivator instead of a plough and direct seeding without any tillage resulted in reductions in soil erosion by 20 to 55 % for conservation tillage and up to 98 % for direct seeding compared to conventional tillage practices. These findings were linked to higher soil aggregate stability, better mulch coverage and increased earthworm abundance in the plot with reduced and no-till applications (NITZSCHE et al., 2001). In their review on problems and opportunities with no-till for crop production and the environment, SOANE et al. (2012) pointed out that no-till can also have negative effects on crop yield and soil properties when applied to unstable or very wet soils without sufficient drainage and hence, that not all soils are suitable for no-till practices. However, a meta-regression analysis on the effects of conservation tillage on crop growth showed that negative effects on yields resulting from conservation tillage are rather limited: combined data from over 47 examined studies suggested a reduction of 4.5 % (PUTTE et al., 2010). Furthermore, this study emphasises the importance of soil and crop type for a successful implementation of conservation tillage.

Decisions on crop type and cultivation period are also the crucial factors for the development of a dense canopy cover and hence, a protection of the bare soil from erosive rainfall. Energy crops, in particular C₄ plants such as maize, millet and sorghum, can increase the soil erosion risk due to late sowing and a delayed establishment of vegetation cover. In order to enhance soil coverage in energy crop cultivation, mixed cultivation, i.e. growing several crops on the same field in the same vegetation period, and double-cropping systems with two crops during one year are promising alternatives to conventional cropping systems.

Mixed cultivation can either comprise the combination of a main crop with catch crops or nurse crops, also called intercropping, or the cultivation of two equal main crops. In several field experiments various combinations of summer and winter crops for energetic use were tested. However, due to fluctuating yields it was concluded that mixed cultivation has positive implications for soil conservation and biodiversity, but is not suitable for achieving higher biomass yields (FNR, 2010). Beneficial environmental effects of growing crops in rotation are widely recognised – not only with regard to soil erosion risk, but also for soil properties (ZEGADA-LIZARAZU & MONTI, 2011). In their review on yields and environmental impacts of energy crops in rotation, ZEGADA-LIZARAZU & MONTI (2011) identify combinations of wheat, maize, sweet sorghum, rapeseed, flax and legumes as most suitable for German growing conditions. Furthermore, for combining only energy crops they suggest growing combinations of maize – sugar beet – sweet sorghum or rapeseed – flax – sunflower in rotation. Another promising approach is energy crop production in double-cropping systems, mainly researched at the University of Kassel-Witzenhausen. Under German conditions a winter-hardy crop is harvested by the end of spring before full ripeness to be used as whole crop silage, directly followed by the sowing of a summer crop, which provides year-round soil cover (GRASS et al., 2013). Furthermore, only conservation tillage and reduced pesticide application are used in this farming system. Analysing results from three years field trials with twelve different double-cropping systems, GRASS et al. (2013) could show that growing maize and rye or maize and rye-pea in double-cropping systems led to higher yields than maize cultivation as the main crop with a catch crop between August and November. Although these results indicate increases in biomass production for energetic uses with the double-cropping system, it is emphasised that even accepting minor reductions in yield might be tolerable in light of higher yield stability (GRASS et al., 2013).

7 Recommendations for Adjustments to Erosion Control Policies

In previous chapters the effectiveness of current erosion control policies was evaluated (Chapter 5) and relevant environmental, management-induced and crop-specific pressures on soil erodibility were reviewed (Chapter 6). In the following, the identified shortcomings in current legislation are discussed (Chapter 7.1) and supplemented by recommendations on adjustments to current erosion control policies (Chapter 7.2). Furthermore, the framework of an Ecological Risk Analysis is used to address environmental risks of energy crops by appropriate soil management strategies (Chapter 7.3).

7.1 Identified Shortcomings in Erosion Control Legislation

Several studies have analysed the current state of soil protection policies in the EU (PALEARI, 2017; TURPIN et al., 2017; FRELIH-LARSEN et al., 2016; GLÆSNER et al., 2014; KUTTER et al., 2011) and they all conclude that soil protection is often rather a by-product of other legislations and therefore current policies on the European level are insufficient to prevent or minimise adverse effects of land use on soil functions.

In the assessment of the current legislation's effectiveness for preventing soil loss by water erosion (Chapter 5), the CAP framework has been identified as the policy instrument setting the most legally binding and concrete requirements for erosion control. Due to the principle of subsidiarity in the EU and federalism in Germany, the task of defining more specific measures and requirements is divided between the federal level in Germany and regional legislation in German federal states. Furthermore, farmers are the stakeholders with the most direct impact on soil resources and they mainly act at regional level. As a result, the focus lies on policies that provide concrete erosion control measures which can be directly linked to farmers' management practices. In the federal system of Germany concrete and binding regulations are set at both national and regional level, whereas the EU provides the broader legal framework. The review of policy documents at national and regional level which correspond to CAP legislation revealed the following weak points in current policies with regard to their effectiveness for preventing soil loss by water:

Scope of Soil Protection Policies

The DirektzahlDurchfG and AgrarZahlVerpflG and the corresponding ordinances implement the EU CAP regulations by specifying concrete measures for erosion control. However, these provisions formally only apply to farmers who receive direct payments as a financial funding. On the contrary, the German BBodSchG requires application of the precautionary principle in all actions related to soil, addressing both landowners and everyone making use of soil resources; however, more specific requirements for the assessment or mitigation of soil erosion risks are set. Even though compliance with GAEC standards can be seen as mandatory as most farmers depend on the CAP-related subsidies, current legislation is lacking specific requirements to consider the local erosion risk in farming decisions regardless of the farmers' participation in funding schemes.

Control and Enforcement Schemes

The categorisation of the local erosion risk is only effective if farmers follow the regulations and consider soil erodibility in their soil management decisions. Compliance with compulsory requirements is controlled and monitored by data collection in an electronic database and on-the-spot checks. Furthermore, in cases of non-compliance direct payments to farmers are normally reduced by 5 to 20 %. In cases of intentional non-compliance, a reduction of 100 % of financial support is possible. However, on-the-spot checks are carried out in only 1 % of farm holdings, which gives very limited insights into the effectiveness of the current approach, whereas only few breaches are categorised as intentional non-compliance (BAYERISCHER LANDTAG, 2017).

Erosion Risk Assessment

The local erosion risk is assessed by the ABAG as stipulated by DIN19708 (2017); however, the analysis of legislation and implementation practice in three federal states has shown that the outcome of the risk assessment process is biased in three ways: firstly, most regional governments decided to consider only two factors (K- and S-factor), which still complies with requirements set in AgrarZahlverpflV. However, the rain erodibility factor (R-factor) can have a major impact on the erosion risk and therefore omitting the R- and also the L-factor inevitably leads to a less exact consideration of natural processes. Secondly, the GIS-analysis has shown that the categorised erosion risk is lower when less recent data with lower spatial resolution is used compared to an assessment based on most recent data. Thirdly, the definition of all DIN erosion risk classes below "very high erosion risk" as "no erosion risk" in the AgrarZahlVerpflG comprises the risk of underestimating local susceptibility to soil erosion by water.

Restrictions to Soil Management

Besides the choice of input variables considered in the local risk calculation, it is the responsibility of the federal states to adjust restrictions to soil management that are imposed on farmland with a high erosion risk. In this way the federal states can take local features into account. However, as the short-term economic interests of farmers are often opposed to measures for soil conservation, local authorities are confronted with a conflict of interest. With regard to GAEC provisions, federal states can influence the restrictions on soil management indirectly by influencing the categorisation of the erosion risk class (see above). If regional authorities advise farmers on how to merge and register their field units to achieve an overall lower risk class, it can be assumed that the effectiveness of erosion control policies is significantly reduced. Even if all reviewed federal states offer financial support for erosion control measures in the scope of AECM, the number and type of measures as well as the corresponding funding vary. As a result some erosion control measures are hardly or not at all remunerated in one federal state, whereas they might receive a high funding in the adjacent region.

7.2 Recommendations on Erosion Control Policies

In anticipation of an increasing demand for biomass in the context of the *Bioeconomy Strategy*, soil protection policies are required to prevent that an expansion in energy crop cultivation leads to increases of soil loss by water erosion. The identified shortcomings in current erosion control policies are relevant for soil conservation regardless of the type of cultivated crops and therefore, erosion control becomes even more urgent when pressures on land resources increase.

In absence of a binding soil protection directive with the requirement to mitigate soil erosion by water and a corresponding enforcement scheme, the CAP regulations are a per se incentive-based, but actually a mandatory policy instrument to implement some erosion control in farming practice. **Even though agricultural land use implies the production of private goods, soils also provide a range of ecosystem services with relevance for the common good (BARTKOWSKI et al., 2018). As soil is a limited resource, soil protection should be mandatory regardless of the farmers dependence on funding schemes.** Reviews of soil governance at both EU and national level come to the conclusion that a common soil conservation policy which addresses all soil functions directly instead of a bundle of policies rather indirectly referring to single aspects would make soil conservation more effective (JUERGES & HANSJÜRGENS, 2018; GLÆSNER et al., 2014; PRAGER et al., 2011). However, the success of such an overarching policy depends very much on effective enforcement schemes and monitoring systems (PRAGER et al., 2011).

Current CAP regulations require on-the-spot checks in 1 % of the subsidised farm holdings and penalties for intentional non-compliance normally amount to 20 % of the direct payments. A brief enquiry from the Greens in Bavaria revealed a correlation of violation of cross-compliance requirements and the proportion of agricultural area with an erosion risk classification (BAYERISCHER LANDTAG, 2017). Obviously, an inspection frequency of 25 to 30 years seems to be insufficient for the prevention of soil loss by water erosion. Furthermore, it remains unclear how intentional non-compliance can be proven by inspectors and which conditions lead to the highest optional penalty of reducing financial support to zero (SMUL, 2018). Also LUPP et al. (2014) conclude in their analysis of legal instruments for sustainable biomass production that current legislation lacks options to sufficiently sanction harmful impacts on ES. **Even though additional controls are obviously limited by administrative and human resources, local authorities should aim for more frequent checks. Furthermore, the enforcement scheme needs to be reformed in order to increase transparency of penalties as well as ensure a sufficient deterrent effect.**

The main derogations to existing provisions for erosion control are made at the regional level of the German federal states. However, by using their legal competence to make amendments to the respective federal laws during the implementation process, local authorities adjust both the erosion risk assessment process and the resulting farming restrictions in areas susceptible to soil erosion. As a result the effectiveness of existing erosion control legislation is often

reduced. **In order to assess the local erosion risk as accurately as possible, the consideration of regional rainfall erosivity – representing one of the main drivers of erosion by water (PANAGOS et al., 2015a) – as well as the use of the most recent data available should be made mandatory.** This data is also used for the compilation of the Erosionsatlas and hence, it requires a political decision rather than high personnel expenditure to use them also for the Erosionskataster. **Furthermore, the introduction of an additional risk class – following the category of "high erosion risk" stipulated by DIN19708 (2017) – is recommended instead of categorising this DIN class as "no erosion risk".** The example of Baden-Wuerttemberg has shown that in regions with very small-scale agriculture, where small fields are merged to larger units, $CC_{\text{wasser}2}$ fields are at risk to "disappear". **The classification of a field as $CC_{\text{wasser}2}$ should result in restrictions to farming practice as well as erosion control measures, without allowing regional authorities to make divergent exemptions for specific farmers.** Increasing the binding force of some provisions at the regional level could also relieve local authorities from balancing interests of farmers and soil conservation. However, PRAGER et al. (2011) found in their field study that making farmers understand and appreciate the purpose of certain measures is a precondition to make GAEC measures effective. **Consequently, a successful implementation of soil conservation measures requires both a working advisory system which is accepted by farmers as well as a good cooperation between environmental and agricultural ministries.**

7.3 Recommendations on a Sustainable Biomass Supply for the Bioeconomy

As not all crops are suitable as biomass feedstock for the production of bioenergy, the implementation of the *Bioeconomy Strategy* requires the cultivation of certain energy crops. The crop-specific impacts of common and potential but scarcely researched energy crops on the erosion risk have been reviewed and summarised in Chapter 6.1. In order to account for the environmental pressures of energy crops on soil resources, the erosion risk assessment should be based on both the local susceptibility of soil to erosion by water and the impact of specific plants on the erosion risk. Currently, the local erosion risk is calculated per field unit and based on soil erodibility (K-factor), slope steepness (S-factor) and possibly rainfall erosivity (R-factor) if the respective federal state chose to include the latter factor in their risk calculation (see subsection 5.2). Following PETERS et al. (2010) and SCHULTZE et al. (2008), who adopted the approach of an Ecological Risk Assessment to evaluate impacts of energy crops on nature functions, this study proposes to integrate an adjusted framework in the legal requirements for erosion risk assessments. The framework aims at, firstly, including the crop-specific pressures in current erosion risk assessment and secondly, adjusting restrictions to soil management according to the erosion risk. This is achieved by overlaying the site-specific vulnerability to soil erosion by water with crop-specific environmental pressures to assess the potential erosion risk and by thereafter linking mitigating measures to certain risk classes.

Intensity

Based on a literature review, plant-specific erosion risks have been assigned to the most common and to potential energy crops in subchapter 6.1. The intensity of the environmental impact of the respective en-

Tab. 12: Energy crops reviewed in Tab.11, grouped by impact intensity

Intensity	Energy Crops
1	Short-rotation coppices, permanent grassland, silphium perfoliatum, switchgrass, giant reed
2	winter cereals, miscanthus
3	rapeseed
4	sunflower
5	maize, sugar beet, potato, sudangrass, sweet sorghum

ergy crop is represented by a value between 1 (low risk) and 5 (high risk). For the Ecological Risk Assessment the reviewed energy crops are grouped according to their erosion risk (Tab.12). If energy crops have been classified differently in the three research studies summarised, the average value is used as the risk value.

Vulnerability

In the proposed framework, the local erosion risk – categorised as CC_{wasser0} , CC_{wasser1} and CC_{wasser2} – represents the vulnerability of a site to soil erosion by water. As stated above, the current classification in the Erosionskataster neglects the erosion risk of many areas due to its high thresholds. Consequently, CC_{wasser0} is treated as the proposed, additional erosion risk class – according to DIN19708 (2017) classified as "high erosion" with soil losses of 7.5 to 15 t/ha yr. Consequently, in this risk assessment only fields with a susceptibility to erosion by water are taken into account and hence, the "no erosion risk" class is not considered in the following framework.

Risk Matrix

The erosion risk is assessed by combining intensity and vulnerability values in a risk matrix (Tab.13). As there are five intensity classes for environmental pressures of energy crops and three vulnerability classes for local conditions it is impossible to weigh both factors equally and have continuously rising risk levels at the same time. By using 1, 2 and 3 as vulnerability values, intensity is automatically weighted more strongly. If vulnerability values are adjusted to cover the same range by using 1, 3 and 5, gaps occur in the distribution of risk levels. For calculating the risk level, values can be summed up or averaged, naturally leading to more extreme values compared to the first method. Furthermore, risk levels vary according to thresholds set for risk level classes. A comparison of different approaches can be found in annex 8.

For the proposed framework the values of both factors were summed up, replacing CC_{wasser0} , CC_{wasser1} and CC_{wasser2} by 1, 2 and 3. The resulting erosion risk was categorised in three classes – low, medium and high risk. The decision of limiting the resulting risk levels to three instead of five classes aims at keeping the differentiation of assessed erosion risk as simple as possible. In this approach intensity of plant-specific environmental impacts is weighted more strongly than local vulnerability as the framework aims for an adjustment of current

risk assessment practice which so far focuses on vulnerability. According to the thresholds set for risk level classes, low risk values and high risk values are distributed evenly, whereas most values are classified as medium risk. The proposed framework envisages requirements for soil conservation measures in energy crop cultivation based on the developed risk matrix (Tab.13). As the framework is used to differentiate energy crop cultivation on those fields that have a known susceptibility to soil erosion by water it is important to notice that no non-vulnerable fields were considered in the assessment. **Consequently, assessing a "low risk" indicates that crop-specific pressures have hardly reinforcing impacts in addition to the local environmental vulnerability – instead of stating that there was only a low erosion risk.** Hence, it is recommended to adjust soil management practice for fields of all three risk classes in order to mitigate the combined environmental pressures on soils when energy crop cultivation coincides with a certain vulnerability for erosion. In the following the risk classes

Tab. 13: Weighted risk matrix by addition of vulnerability and intensity class values. The calculation is weighted as intensity comprises five classes and vulnerability is represented by three classes with the values 1, 2 and 3.

		Vulnerability		
		1 (CC_{wasser0})	2 (CC_{wasser1})	3 (CC_{wasser2})
Intensity	1			
	2			
	3			
	4			
	5			

	Risk Level
	low risk/ A
	medium risk/ B
	high risk/ C

are renamed as *risk class A/B/C* to emphasise that all fields within these categories are prone to soil erosion. Within the scope of the proposed framework the following mitigation measures are recommended:

- **Risk Class A** (low risk): Compliance with tillage ban between 1st December and 15th February as currently stipulated in AgrarZahlverpflV for CC_{wasser1} fields. During the rest of the year soil management is limited to slope-parallel tillage.
- **Risk Class B** (medium risk): Compliance with provisions on year-round reduced soil management, including no tillage between 1st December and 15th February. At all other times soil management is limited to slope-parallel conservation tillage with direct seeding. Furthermore, throughout the year the cropping system should aim at a full vegetation cover by employing double-cropping or intercropping systems.
- **Risk Class C** (high risk): It is not recommended to grow energy crops with such a high impact on the erosion risk on fields with very high susceptibility to soil erosion.

The proposed framework incorporates recommendations from literature as well as results from field experiments (Chapter 6.3). As tillage practice and soil cover are the main impact factors that can be influenced by humans, they should be incorporated by legal requirements

on soil conservation and sustainable land use. The requirements set for the defined risk classes do not aim at replacing, but rather complementing existing recommendations on good agricultural practice. However, it is assumed that the environmental risk of *Risk Class C* cannot be compensated for by erosion control measures in such a way that soil loss can be avoided and therefore, the identified energy crops with high impact intensities should not be grown on fields with high natural erosion risk.

7.4 Limitations

The recommendations given in this chapter are based on a number of assumptions, largely derived from literature. This also had an impact on the focus of this study. In absence of qualitative or quantitative data on the implementation of voluntary measures for erosion control, the analysis on the effectiveness of existing erosion control policies focuses on mandatory measures. Obviously, this view neglects self-motivated commitments to soil conservation as well as complex political negotiations across various hierarchical levels. Consequently, the proposed framework requires additional feedback and input from relevant stakeholders – mainly from farmers and staff of lower governmental authorities.

The suggestions made in section 7.3 for a more differentiated consideration of local factors such as plant-specific impacts on the erosion risk could also be used to integrate soil conservation in general farming practice. However, as the scope of this study is limited to energy crops, the suggested risk assessment framework focusses on making biomass supply for the bioeconomy more sustainable. Moreover, the integration of the proposed framework in current legislation or in a future funding scheme for sustainable biomass production cannot be covered by this study.

The assessment of the crop-specific environmental pressures with regard to erosion by water is based on a review of three scientific reports. Obviously the implementation of such a risk assessment framework requires a more comprehensive assessment of the respective erosion risks, whereas the effectiveness of the suggested mitigation measures has to be based on data from field experiments. Furthermore, for a complete assessment additional environmental factors, such as soil compaction or erosion by wind, should be considered to ensure a sustainable biomass production.

8 Conclusion

The bioeconomy requires large amounts of biomass to replace fossil fuels as a source for energy generation. The expected expansion of energy crop cultivation is likely to increase pressures on soil resources by reducing soil resistance to erosive forces. As soils are considered as a non-renewable resource and, moreover, contribute to several ecosystem services their protection is vitally important. In order to achieve the bioeconomy's objective of sustainable biomass production, environmental policies are required to ensure that increased energy crop cultivation would not compromise soil fertility.

The policy analysis of erosion control policies as well as the GIS-analysis of regional implementation practices has revealed shortcomings of current legislation with regard to the scope of soil protection policies, the corresponding control and enforcement schemes, as well as in the erosion risk assessment process and the resulting restrictions to soil management. Based on this, the following suggestions aim at improving current legislations' effectiveness for preventing soil loss by water: in order to maintain and enhance soil functions, legislation has to set binding standards for soil protection that cannot be overridden by private property rights. As agricultural subsidies require compliance with environmental standards, penalties for non-compliance should be transparent, but also have a sufficiently deterrent effect. As a result of federalism, German federal states can make significant derogations to legal provisions during the implementation process which can decrease the effectiveness of erosion control policies significantly. By increasing the binding force of some provisions, local authorities could be relieved from balancing interests of farmers and soil conservation. By considering regional rainfall erosivity as a compulsory third factor besides slope gradient and soil erodibility and by using most recent data, the representation of local environmental conditions could be improved. Furthermore, including the DIN19708 (2017) category of "high erosion risk" in the Erosionskataster would contribute to a more precautionary risk assessment.

The suggested adjustments to current erosion control policies were also included in recommendations on sustainable energy crop cultivation. Based on the approach of an ecological risk assessment, a framework for the consideration of local environmental and crop-specific factors was proposed. This framework is designed to account for the environmental impacts of expanded energy crop cultivation and could also be used for future funding schemes for sustainable biomass-to-energy production. The categorised plant-specific impact intensity is combined with the local vulnerability, i.e. susceptibility to soil erosion by water, based on three factors (slope gradient, soil erodibility and rainfall erosivity) as suggested above. According to the resulting risk matrix it is recommended to ban the cultivation of energy crops of highest impact intensity from fields with a very high erosion risk (Risk Class C). In general, the erosion risks derived from the risk matrix indicate the more or less reinforcing impact of crop-specific pressures – instead of indicating the final low, medium or high risk. Consequently, adjusted tillage practice and soil cover management are linked to both Risk Class B and A.

However, the proposed framework is a first approach for adjusting current risk assessment practice and hence, it comprises certain limitations. Both the crop-specific erosion risks as

well as the mitigation measures require more comprehensive assessments based on data from field experiments. Field trials are also necessary to evaluate advantages and disadvantages of a weighted risk matrix design, resulting from unequal numbers of factors for intensity and vulnerability. To make biomass production more sustainable, additional environmental pressures of energy crops, such as soil compaction or wind erosion have to be considered.

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Annex

A.1 Ecological Risk Assessment

Tab. 14: Risk matrix by addition of vulnerability and intensity class values. The calculation is weighted as intensity comprises five classes and vulnerability is represented by three classes with the values 1, 2 and 3. Uneven distribution of risk levels, most values in medium risk class

		Vulnerability		
		1 (CC_{wasser0})	2 (CC_{wasser1})	3 (CC_{wasser2})
Intensity	1	2	3	4
	2	3	4	5
	3	4	5	6
	4	5	6	7
	5	6	7	8

	Risk Level
2 – 3	low risk
4 – 6	medium risk
7 – 8	high risk

Tab. 15: Risk matrix by addition of vulnerability and intensity class values. In order to balance the different number of risk classes, the three vulnerability classes enter the calculation with the values of 1, 3 and 5. Even distribution of risk levels. Disadvantage: as no continuous values are used for vulnerability, the resulting risk levels are also irregular. (to avoid this, vulnerability would have to be reclassified to 5 classes).

		Vulnerability		
		1 (CC_{wasser0})	3 (CC_{wasser1})	5 (CC_{wasser2})
Intensity	1	2	4	6
	2	3	5	7
	3	4	6	8
	4	5	7	9
	5	6	8	10

	Risk Level
2 – 4	low risk
5 – 7	medium risk
8 – 10	high risk

Tab. 16: Risk matrix by average calculation of vulnerability and intensity class values. The calculation is weighted as intensity comprises five classes and vulnerability is represented by three classes with the values 1, 2 and 3. Uneven distribution of risk levels with most values in medium risk class.

		Vulnerability		
		1 (CC_{wasser0})	2 (CC_{wasser1})	3 (CC_{wasser2})
Intensity	1	1	2	2
	2	2	2	3
	3	2	3	3
	4	3	3	4
	5	3	4	4

	Risk Level
1	low risk
2 – 3	medium risk
4	high risk

Tab.17 and Tab.18 have the same risk values, just with adjusted risk classes, leading to a distribution of most vs. least values in medium risk class.

Tab. 17: Risk matrix by average calculation of vulnerability and intensity class values. In order to balance the different number of risk classes, the three vulnerability classes enter the calculation with the values of 1, 3 and 5. Uneven distribution of risk levels with least values in medium risk class. Disadvantage: as no continuous values are used for vulnerability, the resulting risk levels are also irregular.

		Vulnerability		
		1 (CC _{wasser0})	3 (CC _{wasser1})	5 (CC _{wasser2})
Intensity	1	1	2	3
	2	2	3	4
	3	2	3	4
	4	3	4	5
	5	3	4	5

	Risk Level
1 – 2	low risk
3	medium risk
4 – 5	high risk

Tab. 18: Risk matrix by average calculation of vulnerability and intensity class values. In order to balance the different number of risk classes, the three vulnerability classes enter the calculation with the values of 1, 3 and 5. Uneven distribution of risk levels with most values in medium risk class. Disadvantage: as no continuous values are used for vulnerability, the resulting risk levels are also irregular.

		Vulnerability		
		1 (CC _{wasser0})	3 (CC _{wasser1})	5 (CC _{wasser2})
Intensity	1	1	2	3
	2	2	3	4
	3	2	3	4
	4	3	4	5
	5	3	4	5

	Risk Level
1	low risk
2 – 4	medium risk
5	high risk

A.2 Difference Map Saxony

Fig. 9: Larger version of the difference map in Chapter 5.2.2. Differences in erosion risk values according to Erosionskataster and Erosionsatlas in Saxony

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